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**Why Some Stay and Others Leave? A Comparative
Study of Retention Factors Affecting Ground-Level
Housekeeping Staff among 3-Star Hotels in Finland
and Sri Lanka**

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ABSTRACT:

The tourism & hospitality industry is one of the largest service-based sectors, contributing significantly to the global economy. The hospitality industry is an exciting business that provides a high-quality experience to guests when they visit particular destinations. Tourists expect a higher level of cleanliness and a better housekeeping atmosphere during their stay at hotels. Therefore, housekeeping services are critical and play a significant role in rendering high-quality service, ensuring guest satisfaction. Housekeeping is the largest workforce in the hospitality industry, with the lowest-paid employees. Housekeeping is regarded by lodging operators as one of the toughest roles in the hospitality sector, resulting in a persistently high turnover rate. While employees are concerned about low pay and bad working conditions, management faces challenges related to rising labour costs resulting from frequent staff turnover. Accordingly, it is important to understand the factors that influence employee retention in hotel housekeeping. However, there is limited research on the retention of ground-level housekeeping employees, particularly in 3-star hotels. Most of the existing studies have concentrated on luxury hotels, managerial-level staff, and general labour issues in the hospitality sector. This leaves a notable gap in understanding factors that affect the retention of housekeeping staff in mid-range hotels. Although employee retention has been widely studied separately in developed and developing countries, it has not been extensively compared across different socio-economic and cultural settings. This study aims to address this gap by comparing a developed country (Finland) with a developing country (Sri Lanka). The objective of this study is to identify key factors influencing the retention of ground-level housekeeping staff in 3-star hotels and to examine how these factors vary across different contextual settings. This study involved eight 3-star hotels, with four selected from each country to ensure balanced representation. The study adopted a mixed-methods and deductive approach. Likewise, the study followed a cross-sectional time horizon. The total population for this study was 140 participants, comprising 120 for the quantitative approach and 20 for the qualitative approach. A sample size consists of 100 for the quantitative analysis and 10 for the qualitative analysis. 61 survey responses were received from the quantitative analysis, and 6 individuals were interviewed as part of the qualitative approach. Data were analysed using SPSS and thematic analysis. Main hypotheses were developed based on identified key organizational factors influencing retention, including remuneration & rewards, training & development, work-life balance, supervisory support, and work stress (H1-H5). To examine contextual influences, sub-hypotheses were also developed (H1a-H5b). In the primary model, training & development emerged as a significant predictor of retention. In the contextual models, remuneration & rewards were the only significant positive predictors in Finland, whereas in Sri Lanka, training & development had a significant impact. These findings suggest that the factors influencing housekeeping staff retention vary across contexts, reflecting variations in socioeconomic and cultural conditions.

KEYWORDS: labour turnover, housekeeping, tourism, hospitality, remunerations, training

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1. Introduction

Tourism is one of the world's largest industries and a main contributor to the global service industry. People have been travelling for pleasure since the dawn of time, and tourism has become one of the fastest-expanding sectors in recent years (Deepthi & Shariff, 2024). Developing countries often promote tourism as a means of economic development, particularly when other options, such as manufacturing or exporting natural resources, are not commercially feasible (Ranasinghe et al., 2020). The hospitality sector is the largest and fastest-growing sector in tourism, which accounts for a considerable portion of the global economy (Morgan & Pritchard, 2018). A new position in hospitality is available every 2.5 seconds (Lüthy, 2025). The hospitality industry is an exciting business that aims to provide a high-quality experience to guests when they visit particular destinations (Perera et al., 2022). Hotels, also known as hospitality businesses, are the most resource-intensive businesses in the hospitality industry (Shantha, 2024). In 2024, the global hospitality market expanded to approximately \$4.9 trillion, driven by increased leisure and pleasure travel, rising international tourism, and higher profits (Lüthy, 2025). Tourists' demand for hotel services includes well-equipped bedrooms, cleanliness, bars and lounges, stylish decorations, exercise facilities, excellent cuisine, and luxurious surroundings. Among these, cleanliness is one of the most important to them (Deepthi & Shariff, 2024). Therefore, housekeeping services are crucial in the hospitality industry, playing a significant role in delivering high-quality service. Generally, the housekeeping department is the largest department within a hotel, with the lowest-paid employees. Upright housekeeping is vital to guest satisfaction and operational success, yet hard for staff, which is why it is recognized as the most challenging department to manage in the hospitality industry (Andrade et al., 2021). Rosemberg (2018) states that the housekeeping employees represent the largest workforce within the hospitality industry, and they are the driving force behind customer loyalty, hotel ratings, and ultimately overall industry growth. However, according to a survey conducted by the American Hotel and Lodging Association (2024), hotels are struggling to find employees, with housekeeping staff experiencing the most acute shortage (Hsieh et al., 2025).

Hence, housekeeping is considered by lodging operators to be among the toughest roles in the hospitality sector, resulting in a persistently high turnover rate. Certainly, high employee turnover in housekeeping is a costly phenomenon in hospitality operations (Huo, 2019, p. 32). While employees are concerned about low pay and bad working conditions, management inevitably worries about increasing labour expenses due to high employee turnover (Davidson et al., 2011, p. 512). Liu et al. (2024) found that employee turnover has many negative effects on organizations. Jayasinghe (2020) states that one of the greatest challenges faced by hotel housekeeping is employee retention. Ma et al. (2025), in an article published in the *Human Resource Management Review*, a leading conceptual journal in the HRM field, highlighted that employee retention is a central concern for scholars and practitioners. Lundberg and Karlsson (2011) further highlight that hotel cleaners often have low salaries, work under poor conditions, and experience higher workplace injuries. Moreover, recent studies indicate that hoteliers struggle to recruit and find it challenging to hire housekeeping staff, even in major cities, and retaining skilled housekeeping staff has become a primary concern of hospitality operations (Huo, 2019).

However, there was not much research conducted on the retention of ground-level housekeeping employees, particularly in 3-star hotels. Most of the existing studies focused on luxury hotels, management-level staff, and general labor issues in the hospitality industry. This leaves a significant gap in understanding factors influencing the retention of ground-level housekeeping staff, who often face the highest employee turnover in the hospitality industry. Employee retention has been widely studied separately in developed and developing countries, but it has not been extensively compared across different socio-economic and cultural settings. Particularly, studies that contrast a developed Nordic country (Finland) with an emerging country like Sri Lanka are rare. Yet, such comparative studies are significant for identifying retention factors that work universally and in each context. A review of “Challenges and Strategies for Employee Retention in the Hospitality Industry” by Ghani et al. (2022) emphasized that the concept of employee retention is broad and many hospitality retention studies

are context-bound. Accordingly, the authors call for research that better accounts for differing contexts, a comparison of the local and the international hospitality industries. Likewise, Han (2020) highlighted the importance of cross-cultural studies in the hospitality industry, and he further mentioned factors predicting turnover such as relationship quality, which works differently in different cultures; it matters in some places but not in China or India. Together, these studies justify the need for research that investigates employee retention across contrasting diverse socio-economic and cultural settings to gain a better understanding of both universal and context-specific determinants. Henceforth, this study answers the call of Presbitero et al. (2016): “future research may consider using more objective measures of retention to ascertain whether employees do stay or not, and track which factors influence employee intention to leave the organization. Equally, this study is answering the call of Huo (2019) who state that “future empirical research could shed light on determining the correlation between demographics such as ethnicity, age, gender, years of experience, and retention factors and defining and constructing the multiple regression analysis by identifying how the weight of each factor contributes to the reasons to stay in the same organization for a long period”. In the same vein, this study responds in part to the call of Andrade, Miller, and Westover (2020) who stated that the “future research should address in more detail the impact pay has on job satisfaction for hotel housekeepers across countries”.

This study is motivated by the need to fill this gap by investigating and contrasting the key factors that influence the retention of ground-level housekeeping staff in 3-star hotels in both countries, Finland and Sri Lanka. The purpose of this study is to tap into this research opportunity by answering "What are the key factors influencing retention of ground-level housekeeping staff in 3-star hotels, and how do these factors similar/differ between Finland and Sri Lanka?" By examining organizational, managerial, socio-cultural, and economic influences in both countries, the study identifies how these variables affect staff retention differently in diverse settings. Most housekeeping staff are represented by ground-level employees, namely room attendants and porters. For this reason, this study primarily focuses on understanding the factors influencing the

retention of ground-level housekeeping staff. Practically, the study findings help hotel management and policymakers to tailor HR practices accordingly. Improving staff retention benefits not only businesses but also employee well-being, particularly their economic security. It is also essential to understand the diverse values and expectations of employees as the world transitions into a more diverse workforce. Academically, a comparative approach contributes a valuable dimension to hospitality research by addressing gaps in cross-cultural labor studies, particularly in mid-range (3-star) hotels, which are often neglected in favor of luxury or budget hotels. Thus, Saehya et al. (2023) acknowledged that housekeeping is an invisible department and, as a result, it has not received such attention from researchers. The study follows a comparative mixed-methods approach combining quantitative and qualitative methods. A cross-sectional design aims to collect data at a single point in time. The study employs survey questionnaires among the housekeeping staff and conducts semi-structured interviews with housekeeping supervisors, managers, and hotel managers. The study will employ a simple random sampling method for the quantitative phase and snowball sampling for the qualitative phase. Quantitative data will be analyzed using SPSS software, followed by descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, and comparative analysis. Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis will be followed to evaluate qualitative data. Then, quantitative and qualitative findings will be triangulated. Ethical considerations of this study include distributing a privacy note, obtaining informed consent from participants, ensuring anonymity and confidentiality, and ensuring voluntary participation.

This study makes three distinct contributions to the literature. First, this study provides comparative cross-cultural insights. Most existing literature has often focused on the context of a single country. For example, Huo (2019) studied employee retention only in the USA, and Aufa et al. (2023) in Indonesia. This inclusive study centralizes novel comparative insights into factors influencing retention of ground-level housekeeping staff in 3-star hotels across Finland and Sri Lanka, in two diverse socio-cultural and economic settings. By contrasting similarities and different causes, the study will provide valuable global cross-cultural insights into employee retention in the hospitality

industry. This comparison will lead beyond the specific local contexts and potentially reveal specific cultural factors that past research has not identified. Secondly, this study addresses a gap in the literature by focusing on ground-level housekeeping staff, including both part-time and full-time staff. In contrast, most existing studies have primarily focused on other hotel departments and full-time staff. For example, Silva and Perera (2020) studied retention of food & beverage staff, and Streeter et al. (2021) studied front office staff. This study addresses the challenges and unique problems faced by ground-level housekeeping staff, a significant but often ignored group among hotel workers. Hence, by examining why ground-level housekeeping staff chose to stay or leave their jobs, the study will provide a better understanding of factors affecting employee turnover in hospitality operations. Likewise, it provides guidelines on how employees can be satisfied and kept in their roles. Thirdly, this study offers contextualized recommendations for 3-star hotels, while most existing studies have focused on employee retention in larger and higher-level hotels. For example, Streeter et al. (2021) studied based on resorts & conventional hotels, and Kumar & Singh (2015) studied selected five-star hotels in Delhi. This study specifically focuses on 3-star hotels, which are an important sector of the hospitality industry and economy, with limited resources. By exploring this particular sector, the study findings provide more tailored and practical recommendations accordingly. Furthermore, this thesis is organized into five main chapters. Chapter one is the introduction, which provides a snapshot of the overall thesis and its structure. Chapter two illustrates relevant literature, key theories, and the developed conceptual framework. Chapter three outlines the methodology for this study, including research approach, design, data collection methods, analysis techniques, and assessment of data quality. Hence, this section provides the necessary information for another researcher to replicate the same, ensuring the reliability and transparency of the current study. Chapter four illustrates findings and results, including data analysis, interpretation, and the identification of patterns and themes. Finally, chapter five discusses theoretical implications, practical Implications, limitations, and suggestions for future research.

2. Literature Review

The literature review of the study consists of four main topics. The first topic, employee retention, covers its definitions, significance, and challenges. The second topic focuses on the tourism and hospitality industry, with subtopics exploring the industry in Finland, Sri Lanka, and housekeeping operations. The third topic addresses factors affecting employee retention, followed by five major factors that are identified and discussed as individual subtopics. Finally, the fourth topic, the developed conceptual framework, is presented for this study.

2.1 Employee Retention

Yamamoto (2013) stated that employee retention is the central idea in Human Resource Management. In the field of Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM), competence retention is recognised as a key area to focus on (Ortlieb & Sieben, 2012). In every industry, employee retention is a significant challenge because high employee turnover leads to failures in achieving organizational objectives (Khalid & Nawab, 2018). Employee retention can be defined as the employer's effort to keep desirable workers to meet business objectives (Fredric et al., 2004). Yamamoto (2009, as cited in Yamamoto, 2013, pp. 14-15) defines retention management as “the entire human resource management policies for retaining the current or expected high-performing employees within organizations for long periods of time, enabling them to exercise or develop their capabilities”. Phillips and Connell (2004) defined retention as the percentage of employees remaining in the organization. Gorde (2019) noted that employee retention is an organization’s ability to retain its employees. He further classified employee retention as a process that aims to motivate and encourage employees to remain with the organization for a longer period. According to him, the ultimate goal of employee retention is to make stakeholders and the employer happier and benefit. Employee retention is essentially the inverse of turnover (Moscelli et al., 2025). Employee turnover is the percentage of employees leaving the organization for

whatever reason(s), which is not a new challenge in today's context, though even greater in the future (Phillips & Connell, 2004).

Retaining employees is central to an organization's long-term success (Khalid & Nawab, 2018). Smith (2011) recognized that employee retention is a crucial element in improving an organization's overall performance. Devi (2023) acknowledged that organizations should strive for employee retention for long-term success. The author further noted that employee retention helps in reducing turnover while minimizing expenses associated with hiring, recruiting, training, and orientation for new employees. Dechawatanapaisal (2017) emphasized that organizations invest heavily in recruiting, selecting, training, and developing employees over time. To maximize the return on these investments, organizations need to retain employees for as long as possible. Chaudhary and Sharma (2023) argued that employee retention reduces turnover costs and prevents the loss of the organization's knowledge, disruption of customer service, and thus increases the organization's reputation and efficiency. Ahammad et al. (2014) highlighted that employee retention is also important for sharing knowledge within a company, particularly, people with special skills or expertise help the company stay ahead of its competitors over time. Cegarra-Leiva et al. (2012) highlighted that business leaders are increasingly aware of employee retention, recognizing it as crucial for achieving a competitive advantage. Hence, Costa and Loureiro (2019) acknowledged that present-day organizations are greatly focused on employees by designing and delivering a better internal experience to retain more talent.

Costa and Loureiro (2019) stated that happy and recognized employees work well and show a higher level of ownership. Thus, they further state that once employees are happy and have good work conditions in terms of financial, physical, and technological aspects, they will go above and beyond to deliver their tasks. Equally, employees will engage and cooperate well with their teammates and other departments. Khan (2020) noted that a dynamic and flexible work culture can be a powerful tool of attraction and retention.

Gorde (2019) identified certain circumstances that lead to employees leaving the organization, including job and person mismatches, lack of appreciation and trust, stress from overwork, work-life imbalance, and a new job offer. He further noted that employee retention does not mean managing retention; it is all about managing people. Hence, if an organization manages its employees well, employee retention takes care of itself. He also recommends that organizations must first understand employee turnover rates over a particular period and benchmark competitors' retention rates. Likewise, Gorde emphasizes the 3Rs of retention. This includes "Respect", "Recognition", and "Rewards". Respect is the admiration, special attention, or thoughtful consideration shown toward people. Respect is a key foundation of retaining employees in an organization, and compared to "Respect" and "Recognition," the "Rewards" have little effect. Recognition provides special attention and the ability to perceive or identify something. Often, retention and morale issues arise due to a lack of attention by management. Rewards are extra perks that an organization offers beyond the fundamentals of "Recognition" and "Respect," expecting to go further than the call of duty. Although "Rewards" represent a small portion of the retention equation, it is still significant.

Basic strategies for employee retention include: hire the right people, trust and respect, empowering, consider employees as the most valuable asset of the organization, equip employees with information and knowledge, provide feedback on employee performance, recognition and appreciation, motivation, and create a comfortable working environment (Gorde, 2019). Igbino et al. (2022) identified that job satisfaction, employee training, rewards, and supervisory support are key components of employee retention strategies. Wahyudi et al. (2023) emphasize that excellent leadership and management help create a positive workplace while encouraging employees to stay. The same study further acknowledged that organizational supports and employee work-life balance led to employee retention; similarly, the contemporary workforce demands opportunities for personal and professional growth over job security. However, Labro & Omartian (2025) stated that employers often respond to

retention concerns by increasing pay and benefits. As noted by Wahyudi et al. (2023), employee retention is a complex challenge with no single solution that works for everyone. Therefore, organizations need to tailor their retention strategies to align with industry demands, workforce demographics, and organizational cultures.

2.2. Tourism & Hospitality Industry

Tourism supports a country's socioeconomic growth and plays a significant role in generating foreign exchange and direct & indirect employment (Thommandru et al., 2023). It has existed since the beginning of human civilization. By the time tourism has taken many different forms, phases, modes, and practices. Although tourism has faced numerous challenges, it has recovered and is playing a significant role in the global economy. The United Nations World Tourism Organization states that tourism has made sustainable growth over the past fifty years, significantly contributing to global economic growth. This includes the national, regional, and international levels. The UNWTO also forecasts that tourism growth will be strong in years when the global economy grows by more than 4%, with tourism typically expanding at a rate 1 to 3 times faster than global GDP (Ranasinghe et al., 2020).

Since the emergence of commercial tourism in the late 1880s, the industry has been facing numerous natural and man-made challenges. However, the global tourism industry was able to grow despite these obstacles. The travel and tourism industry represents the service sector, and it is the world's largest and most diverse industry. Many countries rely on the tourism industry as a primary source for generating revenues, employment, private sector growth, and infrastructure development. Particularly, developing countries encourage tourism development when other forms of economic development, such as manufacturing or the exportation of natural resources, are not commercially viable (Ranasinghe et al., 2020). However, Bunghez (2016) states that tourism encompasses a diversity of activities and showcases the multiplier effect on the economy. Therefore, it is complex links between tourism and other parts of the economy. As claimed by Ranasinghe et al. (2020), mass travel became possible due to a

combination of desire, the ability to move, easy access, and affordable options. In the 20th century, modern technologies, including aviation, computers, robots, and satellite communications, changed the way people live, work, and enjoy their free time. It helped grow mass tourism by giving people more free time, extra money to spend, better ways to communicate, and faster, easier transportation.

Following the severe disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, international tourism showcased a strong recovery in 2023, becoming a key driver of economic growth, job creation, and support for tourism destinations. In 2023, 1.3 billion arrivals were recorded worldwide, 89% recovery from 2019, when arrivals reached 1.5 billion. Likewise, tourism output was USD 3.4 trillion in 2023, accounting for 3% of world GDP (International Tourism Highlights, 2024). Travel & Tourism's contribution to global GDP was US\$10.9 trillion in 2024. This includes direct, indirect, and induced impacts of the sector. Thus, as a share, travel & tourism represented 10% of the global economy. The travel & tourism sector supported a total of 357 million jobs globally in 2024, which is approximately 1 in 10 jobs. Domestic visitors spent US\$5.3 trillion in 2024, and international visitors increased 11.6% annually to reach US\$1.9 trillion (World Travel & Tourism Council, 2025). Moreover, international tourist arrivals increased by 5% in the first quarter of 2025 compared to the same period in 2024. Around 300 million tourists (international) traveled in the first quarter of 2025, about 14 million more than in 2024 (Global Tourism Statistics, 2025).

Morgan and Pritchard (2018) noted that the hospitality industry is one of the largest and fastest-growing sectors in tourism, which accounts for a considerable portion of the global economy. Hence, it has become an increasingly competitive sector in the global economy (Maryam et al., 2025). In 2024, the global hospitality market expanded to approximately \$4.9 trillion, driven by increased leisure and pleasure travel, rising international tourism, and higher profits in line with demand recovery in key regions such as the Middle East and Europe. The World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC) projected that the sector's global economic contribution would reach an all-time high of

\$11.1 trillion in 2024, representing 10% of global GDP. Moreover, in the hospitality industry, a new job opens up every 2.5 seconds. WTTC predicts that by 2034, the sector will employ 449 million people worldwide, representing 12.2 of % global workforce. As per data from THP, there are currently a total of 8,011 hotel opening projects in the pipeline globally, with 2,771 (35%) scheduled to debut in 2025, adding over 514,000 new rooms worldwide (Lüthy, 2025).

As evidenced by Shantha (2024), hotels are the most resource-intensive businesses in the hospitality industry. Frequent changes in global hotel occupancy rates, economic shifts, and evolving consumer preferences underscore the strategic importance of customer retention (Maryam et al., 2025). To provide professional service for guests, destinations, and organizations, a qualified and intelligent workforce is required (Perera et al., 2022). Ranatunga and Dahanayake (2020) noted that the hospitality industry is unpredictable and, therefore, hotel human resources have become crucial to achieving business goals. They further state that the hospitality industry is a highly labor-intensive industry, and retaining non-executive employees is vital as they contribute the highest productivity by directly engaging with guests. Likewise, Perera et al. (2022) noted that the most difficult challenge in the hospitality industry is recruiting and retaining staff due to the high demand for competent individuals and the industry's labor-intensive nature.

2.2.1. Tourism & Hospitality Industry in Finland

Finland's national tourism strategy for 2022–2028 is named 'Achieving more together – sustainable growth and renewal in Finnish tourism'. Finland plans to become the most sustainable tourism destination in the Nordic region, while supporting the economy and creating job opportunities (More together – sustainable growth and renewal for Finnish tourism: Finnish Tourism Strategy 2022–2028 and measures 2022–2023, 2022). Clausnitzer (2024) highlighted that Finland is a growing travel destination in Northern Europe, attracting and increasing the number of international visitors with pristine

nature and distinct regions. International tourist arrivals in Finland more than doubled since 2000, recording 8.9 million visitors in 2019. However, the tourism growth trends have been affected dramatically by the pandemic, but domestic tourism has recovered well. In 2019, tourism generated 16.3 billion euros, and it declined to 15,3 billion euros in 2023. The Finnish hospitality industry contributed 1.8 % of GDP in 2022, compared to 2.7 % in 2019 (MaRa, n.d.). Consistent with the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment of Finland, in 2022, total tourism spending was 14.8 billion euros. This was 31 percent (€3.5 billion) more compared to 2021, but still 9 percent (€1.5 billion) less than in 2019, before the COVID-19 pandemic. Similarly, international tourists spent 3.4 billion euros (23% of the total) in 2022, while Finnish tourists spent 11.4 billion euros (77%). Of that, 9.4 billion euros (65%) came from Finns traveling within Finland.

Clausnitzer (2024) noted that the travel and tourism industry is significant for the growth of the Finnish economy, contributing a share of four percent to the GDP. He further states that the revenue generated by tourism is forecast to exceed 25 billion euros in 2025. The Finnish accommodation sector recorded over 22.83 million overnight stays in 2023, comprising 17 million domestic tourists and 5 million international tourists. Since 2022, the number of international tourists in Finland has considerably grown, especially in Lapland and the capital region. Most of the international tourists visited Finland from Germany, followed by the United Kingdom, Sweden, and Estonia.

The Finnish tourism sector's contribution to GDP was expected to grow by 1.7 percentage points from 2023 to 2028. However, it's predicted to go down slightly in 2026, 2027, and 2028. By 2028, the expected contribution to GDP by tourism is 7.07%. Although tourism is forecast to grow in the coming years, the pace of growth is likely to slow down in the later years (Statista, 2025). Clausnitzer (2025) noted that there were approximately 1,200 travel accommodations in Finland. Out of these, 650 were hotels and 540 other accommodation establishments. The number of accommodation establishments was slightly increased in 2023 compared to the previous year, 2022. Moreover, the overall accommodation occupancy rate in Finland gradually increased

from 2013 to 2023. In 2023, the occupancy rate of bed places in hotels and similar establishments was 39.93% compared to 38.04% in 2022, an increase.

Examined by the tourism industry, 52% employees work in the food & beverage sector, 23% work in passenger transport services, and the remaining 25% represent cultural, sport, recreational services, accommodation services, travel agencies, and similar services (Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment of Finland, n.d.). The Finnish hospitality sector reported 140,600 employees in 2022, of whom 30% were under 26 years of age. The Finnish hospitality industry's workforce increased by 21 % between 2006 and 2019, while traditional manufacturing industries reduced their workforce (MaRa, n.d.). Based on statistics (January-May 2024), 7,000 job vacancies are open each month in accommodation, food and beverage services, and tourism services. However, Russia's war against Ukraine, the COVID-19 pandemic, and general geopolitical and economic uncertainty have increased the tourism sector labor shortage and the challenge of matching supply and demand in occupations. The unemployment rate in the tourism sector was recorded as 13%. Similarly, 15,000 unemployed job seekers were verified per month. The accommodation and restaurant sectors were recorded with atypical employment (part-time & short fixed-term work for less than 3 months) of open vacancies at 57% in 2023, and 69% 2022. This indicates that more than half of all open vacancies in the accommodation and restaurant sectors were temporary agency work. In comparison to available job vacancies in the tourism sector, 98% occupations have earnings under 16 euros per hour, which is lower than the median wage of employees, 18.41 euros per hour in 2020. Hence, 46% of available occupations have an hourly salary of less than 16 euros. Approximately 70% of employees in the accommodation and food & beverage service sector were women, and foreign employees in the sector were 23% in 2022 (Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment of Finland, n.d.).

The Confederation of Finnish Industries stated that staff turnover in tourism and restaurant services is higher than in other sectors. The gross turnover percentage in tourism and restaurant services was 35 % in 2020–2021 (Ministry of Economic Affairs

and Employment of Finland, n.d.). During 2019 - 2020, the tourism sector turnover was recorded at 34.3%. Moreover, in the tourism sector, the number of people leaving was higher than the number of people entering, 37% and 33.6% respectively (Mankki, 2022).

2.2.2. Tourism & Hospitality Industry in Sri Lanka

Sri Lankan tourism industry figures significant tourist arrivals in 2024, welcoming 2,053,465 international tourists compared to 2023. January recorded the most substantial growth rate in terms of tourist arrivals, soaring by 103.08% from the previous year. As September is off-peak season, it recorded the lowest tourist arrivals growth rate, indicating 9.11%. December recorded 248,592 visitors, the highest number of arrivals, likely influenced by winter vacations and other favorable conditions. In comparison of tourist arrivals by region, Europe accounts for 50.67% of total arrivals, which is the highest proportion. The Asia Pacific region is the second-largest source market, accounting for 41.91% of arrivals. Similarly, the Americas accounted for 5.29% of the arrivals, and the Middle East and Africa recorded smaller shares of 1.42% and 0.7%, respectively (Year in Review 2024, 2025). However, SLTDA expected 2,676,596 tourist arrivals in 2025 and, in an optimistic situation, up to 3,000,000 (Growth Scenarios for Tourism to Sri Lanka 2025, 2025). Moreover, from January to June 2025, Sri Lanka recorded 1,168,044 tourist arrivals (Monthly Tourist Arrivals Reports 2025, 2025)

In 2024, the top ten tourism source markets for Sri Lanka were led by India, which contributed 20.3% of total tourist arrivals, followed by the Russian Federation with a 9.8% share. The United Kingdom, Germany, and China contributed 8.6%, 6.6%, and 6.4% respectively. Australia contributed 4.4% while France and the United States contributed 4.3% and 2.9% respectively. The Netherlands contributed 2.4% and the Maldives 2.3%. The majority of tourists visiting Sri Lanka are on pleasure and vacation purposes. In numbers, 50.8% of the United Kingdom, 41.5% of Russians, 37.9% of Germans, 37.9% of Chinese, and 33.9% of Indians. In addition to leisure purposes, a notable number of tourists visited friends and relatives, for instance, 19.8% of Australian tourists, 11.8% of Americans, and 10.9% Britons. The MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and

Exhibitions) sector also contributes to Sri Lanka's tourism, with of 9.2% Russian tourists, 5.7% of French tourists, and 3% of Indian tourists. Wellness tourism is also an emerging sector in Sri Lankan tourism, and the majority of German tourists visit for wellness, such as Ayurveda and spa retreats (Year in Review 2024, 2025).

In terms of tourist stay duration, tourists from the Netherlands exhibit the longest average stay, approximately 14.47 nights, followed by tourists from Switzerland and Israel. Similarly, Russian tourists tend to stay longer, with an average of 9.93 nights. Indian tourists, who contribute the largest market to Sri Lankan tourism, occupy an average of 5.27 nights. In contrast, Bangladeshi tourists recorded the shortest average stay in Sri Lanka, around 4.89 nights. Yet, the average duration of stay for Sri Lanka is recorded as 8.42 nights. Sri Lankan tourism attracts a nearly equal proportion of male and female tourists. It figured 51% and 49% respectively. Moreover, the 31-40 age group represented the largest segment (22.5%) of tourist arrivals in Sri Lanka. Tourists aged 60 and above accounted for a notable 17.2% of total arrivals, and the 41-50 age group represented 17.7%. Tourists, aged 51-60, made up 15.2% of arrivals, and the 20-30 age group constituted 16.4% of arrivals (Year in Review 2024, 2025).

In 2024, Sri Lanka's tourism revenue was recorded as 3,168.601 USD Mn. Receipt per tourist per day/ average expenditure per day accounted for 181.15 USD (Year in Review 2024, 2025). The direct contribution to the GDP by travel & tourism in 2023 was LKR 690.3 billion (2.2% of GDP) and is expected to grow by 7.1% pa to LKR 1,808.7 billion (3.6% of GDP) from 2024 to 2034. Travel & Tourism generated 209,174 jobs directly in 2023, which was 2.6% of total employment. However, by 2034, it is expected to account for 425,224 jobs directly, 5.1% of total employment. In 2023, domestic travel spending was 46.4% of total internal spending (LKR 807.7 billion). In comparison, foreign visitors spent more, making up 53.6% or LKR 934.1 billion. By 2034, international visitor spending is expected to account for LKR 3.02 trillion and domestic visitor spending for LKR 1.49 trillion (Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2024, 2024).

The Sri Lankan Hospitality market size is valued at USD 470.76 million. It is expected to grow by a CAGR of 7.5% during the forecast period. The hospitality sector is a key component of the Sri Lankan tourism industry, and thus, a wide variety of hospitality options are available. The third largest revenue source in Sri Lanka is tourism, and hence, the hospitality sector significantly contributes to generating foreign earnings (Hospitality Industry In Sri Lanka - Market Share Analysis, Industry Trends & Statistics, Growth Forecasts 2020 - 2029, 2024). By the end of 2024, the total number of SLTDA-registered accommodation establishments in Sri Lanka was 4,519, which accounts for a total of 55,455 rooms. Among them, 169 were “Classified Tourist Hotels”, which contributed 17,182 rooms to the industry. Out of 169 classified tourist hotels, 31 are designated as five-star establishments. The hospitality accommodation sector is predominantly subsidized by small and medium businesses (SMEs). These included 1,687 guest houses, 1,122 homestays, and 1,111 bungalows. Guest houses contributed the largest share at 37.3%, followed by homestays at 24.8%, and bungalows at 24.5%. However, the classified tourist hotels showcase only 3.7% of the total (Year in Review 2024, 2025).

2.2.3. Hotel Housekeeping

The main responsibility of hotel housekeeping is to clean and maintain the hotel’s guest rooms and other areas. The size and setup of the housekeeping department can vary depending on the hotel’s type, size, services offered, category, and level of occupancy (Batinić, 2015). Hotel housekeeping is one of the most critical functions in any lodging operation. While guests often take a clean room for granted, hospitality managers understand that poor housekeeping is one of the leading causes of guest dissatisfaction (Lourdes & Hadi, 2025). Andrade et al. (2021) state that generally, the housekeeping department is the largest department within a hotel, followed by the lowest-paid department. They further acknowledged that housekeeping is vital to guest satisfaction and operational success, yet tough to staff, which is why it is recognized as the most challenging department to manage in the hospitality industry. Rosemberg (2018) states that the housekeeping employees represent the largest workforce within the hospitality

industry, and they are the driving force behind customer loyalty, hotel ratings, and ultimately overall industry growth. However, as per a survey conducted by the American Hotel and Lodging Association (2024), hotels are struggling to find employees, with housekeeping staff experiencing the most acute shortage (Hsieh et al., 2025).

The hotel's housekeeping is operating 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, all year round. Apart from the hotels, trained housekeeping staff are also needed on cruise ships and in other luxury places. Nowadays, many of these organizations prefer to hire housekeeping from outside companies, so contract housekeeping has become popular (Chatterjee, 2022). The efficiency of the housekeeping department ensures cleanliness, preservation, and the aesthetic appeal of a hotel. The housekeeping daily tasks are vital to the smooth day-to-day functioning of a lodging establishment. In today's highly competitive hospitality industry, housekeeping operations present significant challenges, and meeting guest expectations consistently is even more demanding (Jayasinghe, 2020).

A housekeeper's job is significantly harder compared to other jobs in the tourism industry. It involves tough working conditions, a high risk of accidents and work-related illnesses, low pay, and meagre respect or recognition from society (Alcalde-González et al., 2021). Rosemberg (2018) states that the housekeeping staff often recorded high rates of occupational health risks, unstable employment conditions, and adverse health outcomes. He further acknowledged that the hotel housekeeping employees experience a significant imbalance between the effort they invest and the rewards they receive, which is accompanied by reduced work productivity.

At present, hotel executive housekeepers face challenges that require a high level of professionalism. The role of the housekeeping department has changed; in the past, housekeeping primarily focused on preparing clean guest rooms. But today, housekeeping encompasses a broader set of responsibilities aligned with modern hospitality standards. At the same time, the most pressing issue is employee retention.

Many hotels now invest more time and resources in retaining housekeeping staff, as they understand the costs associated with high turnover, recruitment, and training (Jayasinghe, 2020). The common perception of housekeeping often leads to a 'dirty' or undesirable job, following ongoing labour shortages. This highlights the importance of exploring how housekeepers see their work, including what they value and the challenges they face in the profession (Hsieh et al., 2025).

2.3. Key Factors Affecting Employee Retention

Identified key employee retention factors include remuneration & rewards, training & development, work-life balance, supervisory support, and work stress. The following literature review examines each of the retention factors separately.

2.3.1. Remuneration & Rewards as a Key Factor in Employee Retention

As explained by Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959), salary is a hygiene factor, indicating that better pay avoids employee dissatisfaction, turnover, and increases retention (Shinde, 2025). Huang (2016, as cited in Milkovich, Newman, & Gerhart, 2014, p. 10) defines pay as "all forms of financial returns and tangible services and benefits employees receive as part of an employment relationship". A review of the HRM literature recognized that better remuneration, including pay packages and benefits, contributes to employee retention. An overall remuneration package that includes a base salary and benefits such as bonuses, hospitalisation insurance, and health club membership seems to be attractive when it matches or exceeds what is common in the industry (Presbitero et al., 2016). Hence, organizations adopt various pay systems to enhance productivity and competitiveness (Sweins et al., 2009). Krishna et al. (2022) acknowledged that compensation packages provide basic features of employee satisfaction and retention, including wages, benefits, and promotions. Došenović (2016) noted that employee rewards are key resources that involve money, goods, and services

employees receive in return for their work. He further stated that a well-designed employee reward system is vital to effective job performance and business stability.

The study on “Understanding Factors Influencing Employees’ Retention in an Organization Today” found that 77% of respondents agreed that employees often leave their current jobs in search of better compensation packages. Therefore, organizations must recognize this as a key push factor; if ignored, it can lead to the loss of valuable and reliable staff (Lagu, 2019). Syahreza et al. (2017) acknowledged that compensation has a higher effect on employee retention because when employees receive satisfactory compensation, they feel the organization cares about them. “A study on compensation's impact on employee retention” showcases that a structured and transparent compensation system is essential for retaining employees. However, the study further states that the monetary benefits on their own do not guarantee employee loyalty (Kavika & Kumar, 2025).

As outlined by Sorn et al. (2023), employee retention is a significant challenge for both large and small businesses. Although numerous factors influence employee retention, compensation is one of the most crucial. To improve employee retention, organizations should take a comprehensive approach by offering competitive pay while also addressing other factors that are important to employees. Ojediran and Adebayo (2023) stated that adequate and sustainable remuneration has a stronger impact on employee retention than high compensation alone. Moreover, Krishna et al. (2022) identified that compensation practices have a strong influence on employee performance and retention. They further noted that compensation practices provide employers with various ways to reward employees, serving as a key motivator.

2.3.2. Training & Development as a Key Factor in Employee Retention

Today, organizations are increasingly investing in training & development programs to enhance employees' skills, knowledge, and competencies. In return, this leads to higher

employee engagement, greater job satisfaction, and ultimately employee retention (Mishra, 2023). Ng and Dastmalchian (2011) claimed that, although training is a key HRM area, literature has been largely overlooked. From the Social Exchange Theory (1964) view, when organizations provide training & development opportunities, employees feel that the company is investing in them. Therefore, they feel a sense of obligation to give something back, including loyalty, commitment, and retention (Xuecheng et al., 2022). Likewise, Herzberg's theory suggests achievement and personal growth as motivators, which are consequently central to job satisfaction and employee retention (Shinde, 2025). Recent research highlights the important role of organizational identification in connecting training and development to employee retention. Effective training not only enhances skills and job satisfaction but also strengthens employees' sense of belonging to the organization, which maximizes employee retention (Farrossabilla & Maksum, 2025). Continuing employee development and training opportunities are associated with employees' intention to stay in their current job, avoiding job changes, and delaying early retirement (Shiri et al., 2023).

Mishra (2023) stated that learning & development programmes have a favourable effect on employee retention. Thus, learning and development activities advance employee happiness and engagement, which ultimately results in a higher retention rate. He further acknowledged that learning and development programmes can be used as a successful tactic for increasing staff retention. Dietz and Zwick's (2022) study confirmed a significant positive effect of training and retention. Likewise, Fletcher (2018) found that perceived training & development is positively associated with employee retention. The study by Presbitero et al. (2016) identified a positive and significant relationship between training and development and employee retention. Equally, Farrossabilla and Maksum (2025) acknowledged that training development positively and significantly influences employee retention. The study on "Relationship between perceived training and development and employee retention: the mediating role of work attitudes" found that training & development are positively associated with employees' intention to stay (Fletcher et al., 2016). Nonetheless, Finegold et al. (2005) go beyond and found that less

than 25% of temporary workers receive training, and lower-skilled workers are more willing to attend training, while educated and experienced individuals are more likely to be offered training.

Training & development programs make employees feel obligated and loyal to the organization. When employees are obliged and committed, they are more likely to stay for a long time. Training & development also shows employees that the organization trusts and supports them, which decreases their desire to leave (Muhammad & Bowra, 2020). Furthermore, Merican et al. (2022) stated that career planning, training, development, and talent management are significant and positively correlated with employee retention.

2.3.3. Work-life Balance as a Key Factor in Employee Retention

Work-life balance is becoming a significant factor in workplaces in line with today's busy environment. When organizations neglect the importance of work-life balance, it can lead to negative impacts on employees, including employee turnover. Therefore, organizations must practice work-life balance, which helps keep their employees with themselves (Hashim et al., 2016). As observed by Sumanarathna and Samarakoon (2019), work-life balance is a compulsory practice in today's business organizations to motivate employees, retain them, and sustain profitability. They further stated that people work to earn money to live and to fulfil the needs and wishes of their loved ones. But if they do not have enough time to spend with their loved ones due to their employment, it creates a gap between work life and personal life. Likewise, Gimpal (2024) highlighted the importance of work-life from the perspective of Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene theory and further emphasized that it promotes both satisfaction and retention in today's workforce. However, there is substantial debate about how management practices affect work–life balance (Heywood et al., 2010).

Today, organizations recognise that work-life balance (WLB) programs are an essential tool for retaining talented employees, increasing job satisfaction, and reducing employee turnover. However, their success depends on how well they are designed, communicated, and fit the organization's culture (Rajkumar et al., 2025). Cegarra-Leiva et al. (2012) found that work-life balance improves retention while contributing to job satisfaction. Likewise, Sheshadri et al. (2024) noted a significant positive relationship between work-life balance (WLB) and employee retention. They further acknowledged that organizations' practices of work-life balance tend to have lower turnover rates. Gbajumo-Sheriff et al. (2024) stated that there is a consequential connection between employee retention and work-life balance. However, the connection is based on factors such as policy support, awareness of programs, flexibility of schedules, support for family responsibilities, communication policies, recommendations for changes, and contribution to job satisfaction. Thereby, organizations should focus on these initiatives if they need to improve both work-life balance and employee retention. Moreover, Lamane-Harim et al. (2023) noted that organizations should create various strategies to promote better work-life balance beyond legal requirements. The authors further emphasized the importance of encouraging men's work-life balance practices as they often experience higher work–family conflict.

The study of Montaña (2025) confirms a strong relationship between work-life balance and employee retention intention. Hence, as modern workplaces become more complex, organizations focus on work-life balance practices as a key strategy. Furthermore, the study recognised that when employees feel they have a balance between work and personal life, they are more satisfied, loyal, and less likely to quit. Similarly, the study by Hashim et al. (2016) confirmed a positive relationship between work-life balance and employee retention. Tumati and Al-Salmi (2023) stated that work-life balance practices support employee retention and career growth. According to them, work-life balance initiatives are vital for hotel businesses, and they help manage employees' personal and working lives. Flexible working hours are striking a balance between hotel employees' jobs and their personal lives. Henceforth, career breaks are

another useful work-life balance practice that encourages employees to stay with the company. However, Chandra (2012) goes further and argues that most existing studies on work-life balance (WLB) come from Western countries, where views and practices differ; in contrast, Asian countries often treat WLB mainly as a women's issue. The author further emphasized the need for a flexible WLB model that fits various individuals' needs.

2.3.4. Supervisory Support as a Key Factor in Employee Retention

A successful implementation of HR policies rests largely on supervisors being actively involved in the process (Straub et al., 2018). Supervisors play a significant role in the organization by guiding employee behaviour, managing work processes, and acting as a connection between different teams and departments. Supervisory support enhances employee retention in organizations by making them feel more confident and motivated. Appropriate supervisory support and resources lead employees to feel empowered, capable in their roles, and increase retention intention. Hence, positive supervisory support also encourages employees to go above and beyond their regular duties to benefit the organization (Mittala & Kaur, 2022). Consistent with social exchange theory, when employees recognize that their supervisors care and support their well-being, they feel more connected with the organization. As a result, employees are more likely to retain and remain loyal to the organization (Gentry et al., 2006).

As revealed by Khan (2021), supervisory support reduces employee turnover and improves their chances of staying with the company, such as retention intention. He further acknowledged that supportive supervisors often use a 360° performance appraisal. Meacham et al. (2023) confirmed that supervisory support drops turnover intention. Likewise, Malik et al. (2020) state that if supervisors support employees and treat them well, it is beneficial for the organization, as perceived supervisor support and retention have a strong positive relationship. The study on "Understanding the role of supervisor support in retaining employees and enhancing their satisfaction with life"

found that supervisor support was positively related to quality of work life (QWL). Accordingly, a better QWL was linked to higher commitment to the organization and greater life satisfaction, and finally to lower turnover intentions (Rathi & Lee, 2017). Hence, Park and Jang (2017) found that greater supervisory support maximizes employee mental health, which consequently leads to retention.

Gentry et al. (2006) acknowledged that supervisory support is significant in retaining part-time employees (PTEs) in the organization. Furthermore, the study by Modaresnezhad et al. (2021) indicates that supervisor support weakened the job dissatisfaction-turnover relationship. However, the study “Supportive supervisors: the key to employee retention?” (2020) found that perceived supervisor support does not have a significant direct effect on turnover intention. Yet it found an indirect significant relationship between perceived supervisor support and turnover intention.

2.3.5. Work Stress as a Key Factor in Employee Retention

Work-related stress has risen significantly in recent years. Hence, it increases organizations' costs and economic costs while reducing employee well-being (Weiß, 2020). Workplace stress has become a significant challenge for organizations globally due to its negative impact on employee health, productivity, and organizational sustainability. People experience stress at work in different ways based on their job role, employment duration, management relationship, and expectations. For instance, front-of-house employees face higher emotional stress as they often interact with customers. In contrast, the back-of-house employees may feel pressure to be efficient and meet deadlines. Particularly, the hotel industry is exposed to high levels of occupational stress as it is a service-intensive and labor-dependent sector (Asier et al., 2025). Moreover, Kim et al. (2022) identified that working 'over time' is a key contributor to employee work stress. Masood (2013) acknowledged three types of stress that occur at the workplace, including physical stress, emotional or mental stress, and behavioral stress. Physical stress arises when aligning with ergonomics, such as providing space for work,

equipment, comfort, lighting, and ventilation. Emotional and mental stress is unique for each individual's personality, attitude, preferences, perceptions, and mindset, and thus it is complex and even confusing. Behavioral stress is the stress that results from the behavior of oneself or others. However, the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) model can be used to identify which job stressors and which supports affect burnout and employee retention (Scanlan & Still, 2019). The JDR model proposes that every job has two features, job demands and job resources (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2018).

The study on “Workplace Stressors and the Intention to Quit: The Role of Psychological Distress and Psychological Flexibility Among Hospitality Employees” acknowledged that higher stress at work is linked to feeling more mentally distressed and a stronger intention to quit employment (Asier et al., 2025). Liu et al. (2019) noted that work stress showcases a positive and ancillary impact on employee turnover intentions. As reported by Masood (2013), the outcome of job stress is negative and results in absenteeism, ineffectiveness, dissatisfaction, and turnover. Likewise, Yu (2023) found a strong correlation between job stress and job burnout. Similarly, he further identified a strong correlation between job stress and the employee's intention to leave.

Salama et al. (2022) noted that work stress arises when workers are unable to handle ongoing pressure, which leads to job burnout. This is a serious occupational health issue leading to job dissatisfaction, emotional imbalance, and lower productivity. Over time, these fallouts include boredom, depression, and employee turnover. A study, “A Threat of Customer Incivility and Job Stress to Hotel Employee Retention: Do Supervisor and Co-Worker Supports Reduce Turnover Rates?” identified that job stress is a significant influence on increasing turnover intention (Chung et al., 2021). Moreover, Lan et al.'s (2019) study showed a significant correlation between organizational job stress, workplace burnout, and employee retention.

2.4. Conceptual Framework

Based on the literature review, key factors influencing employee retention were identified. The key employee retention factors, serving as independent variables, include remuneration & rewards, work stress, training & development, work-life balance, and supervisor support. Employee retention, covering both full-time and part-time staff, serves as the dependent variable. The study also incorporates moderating variables, representing the contextual comparison between Finland (Developed) and Sri Lanka (Developing). Accordingly, the conceptual framework (Figure 01) was developed to examine the factors affecting the retention of full-time and part-time housekeeping staff in 3-star hotels across Finland and Sri Lanka. The relationships are first hypothesized in a general form (Main), and then extended to sub-hypotheses that consider cross-country differences between Finland and Sri Lanka.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

Remuneration & Rewards towards Retention

Compensation is widely recognized as a key factor influencing employee retention. Employees who receive satisfactory rewards & remuneration are more likely to be

retained in current employment. Fair remuneration & rewards satisfy both economic and psychological needs. However, the degree to which remuneration & rewards influence retention may differ across countries or contexts.

Main hypothesis:

- H1: Higher perceived remuneration & rewards are positively associated with ground-level housekeeping staff retention. ($\beta_1 > 0$)
- H1₀: Remuneration & rewards are not positively associated with ground-level housekeeping staff retention. ($\beta_1 \leq 0$)

Sub-contextual hypothesis:

In a developed country like Finland, where remuneration & rewards are often higher and standard labour laws are regulated, remuneration may serve as an important factor. Yet, it may not be an exclusive determinant of employee retention. By contrast, in Sri Lanka, remuneration & rewards are more critical in terms of employee financial security, which is a primary driver of employment decisions and retention. Given these contextual distinctions, this study empirically examines whether perceived remuneration & rewards are positively associated with staff retention in both countries, or whether the relationship differs between the two contexts.

- H1a: In Finland, higher perceived remuneration & rewards are positively associated with staff retention.
- H1b: In Sri Lanka, higher perceived remuneration & rewards are positively associated with staff retention.

Training & Development towards Retention

Employee training & development often strengthen employees' organizational commitment. It improves employee performance, enhances employability, loyalty, and retention. Although this is commonly believed, it may still vary depending on an individual's perception, experience, culture, and context.

Main hypothesis:

- H2: Greater training & development are positively associated with ground-level housekeeping staff retention. ($\beta_3 > 0$)

- H2_o: Training & development are not positively associated with ground-level housekeeping staff retention. ($\beta_3 \leq 0$)

Sub-contextual hypothesis:

In developed countries such as Finland, training & development are identified as key components of career and professional development. Therefore, the absence of development programs may lead to turnover intention and reduce retention. Conversely, Sri Lanka performs relatively limited training & development programs, and offering such programs can have a positive and strong effect on employee retention. Accordingly, this study empirically explores the extent to which perceived training & development opportunities are linked to employee retention in each context and examines whether the strength of this association varies across the two countries.

- H2a: In Finland, greater training & development are positively associated with staff retention.
- H2b: In Sri Lanka, greater training & development are positively associated with staff retention.

Work–Life Balance towards Retention

Work–life balance is a crucial factor in today’s busy environment. This is significant in a service-based industry like hospitality, as the industry is dominated by shift work and 24/7 operations. It is commonly recognised that the work-life balance influences employee satisfaction, and those who can balance personal obligations with work requirements are more likely to remain in their jobs. However, this may be affected differently in various contexts, depending on employees’ culture, values, and lifestyles.

Main hypothesis:

- H3: Better work–life balance is positively associated with ground-level housekeeping staff retention. ($\beta_4 > 0$)
- H3_o: Work–life balance is not positively associated with ground-level housekeeping staff retention. ($\beta_4 \leq 0$)

Sub-contextual hypothesis:

Work-life balance in Finland is strongly encouraged by the working culture. Any imbalance is likely to limit employee retention. In a developing country like Sri Lanka, work-life balance is still expected to have a positive effect on retention; however, employees may prioritize their financial security over work-life balance. Therefore, this study empirically examines whether perceived work-life balance is positively associated with staff retention in both Finland and Sri Lanka, and whether the strength of this association varies across the two countries.

- H3a: In Finland, a better work–life balance is positively associated with staff retention.
- H3b: In Sri Lanka, a better work–life balance is positively associated with staff retention.

Supervisory Support towards Retention

Supervisory support enhances employee engagement, motivation, and a sense of belonging. This consequently leads to reduced employee turnover intention and fosters retention. It is widely recognised that staff who receive strong support from their supervisors are more likely to retain their employment and are often more committed to the organization. However, the rationale and importance of supervisory support may differ among employees in different contexts.

Main hypothesis:

- H4: Stronger supervisory support is positively associated with ground-level housekeeping staff retention. ($\beta_5 > 0$)
- H4₀: Supervisory support is not positively associated with ground-level housekeeping staff retention. ($\beta_5 \leq 0$)

Sub-contextual hypothesis:

Supervisory support is a significant factor for both contexts, Sri Lanka and Finland. It really does not matter whether the context is developed or emerging. Supportive supervision in Finland can further strengthen the work culture and employee well-being. By contrast, in Sri Lanka, strong supervisory support can mitigate work stress and may

reduce employees' intentions to seek other job opportunities. Considering these contextual differences, this study empirically investigates whether perceived supervisory support is positively related to staff retention both in Finland and Sri Lanka, and whether the strength of this association varies across the two contexts.

- H4a: In Finland, stronger supervisory support is positively associated with staff retention.
- H4b: In Sri Lanka, stronger supervisory support is positively associated with staff retention.

Work Stress towards Retention

Higher levels of work stress are often associated with poor employee well-being and, consequently, increase employee turnover intentions. Particularly, industries like hospitality experience higher work stress at work due to irregular working hours, heavy workloads, and customer service pressures. Hence, the housekeeping department is the worst among all departments. However, the impact of work stress may still vary depending on context and the employee's perception. For example, some employees may view stress as a normal part of working in the hospitality industry.

Main hypothesis:

- H5: Higher perceived work stress is negatively associated with ground-level housekeeping staff retention. ($\beta_2 < 0$)
- H5₀: Work stress is not negatively associated with ground-level housekeeping staff retention. ($\beta_2 \geq 0$)

Sub-contextual hypothesis:

In developed countries like Finland, employees are prioritized with a balanced workload and psychological needs. Therefore, work stress is likely to have a strong negative impact on employee retention. However, employees in emerging countries like Sri Lanka may tolerate higher stress due to a lack of job opportunities and economic challenges, yet can also experience negative consequences such as turnover intention. Taking these contextual differences into account, this study empirically examines the relationship

between perceived work stress and retention in both Finland and Sri Lanka, and evaluates how the strength of this connection differs between the two contexts.

- H5a: In Finland, higher perceived work stress is negatively associated with staff retention.
- H5b: In Sri Lanka, higher perceived work stress is negatively associated with staff retention.

Summary

The hypothesis outlined above combines the general relationships (H1 to H5) and the country-specific hypotheses (H1a to H5a and H1b to H5b). This structure allows the study to understand not only how organizational factors affect retention, but also how those effects vary across different contexts (Finland versus Sri Lanka or Developed versus Emerging). Likewise, it provides a deeper understanding of how cultural, institutional, and economic differences shape employee retention in hotel ground-level housekeeping staff.

3. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods employed in the study, including the research philosophy, approach, methodological choices, strategy, time frame, procedures, and techniques. The chapter is organized under the following headings: research design, case firms, population and sample, data collection, measures, data analysis, and an evaluation of data quality.

3.1. Research Design

The study followed the business research model, namely the research onion (Figure 02), developed by Saunders et al. (2019). The research onion comprises various layers or steps in the research design process, together with research philosophy, approach to developing theory, methodological choice, strategy, time horizon, procedures, and techniques (Saunders et al., 2023). Designed a research onion for this study, as shown in Figure 02.

Figure 2. Research Onion: Adopted from Saunders et al. (2023)

Research philosophy

The study followed pragmatist philosophy. The idea of adopting a pragmatist research philosophy is that it allows focus on what works best in solving a problem, rather than being stuck with one method or theory. Hence, the phenomenon of employee retention of ground-level housekeeping staff cannot be fully understood through a single lens. Retention may depend on both quantifiable factors, such as remuneration, work stress, and career growth, as well as subjective factors, including work relationships and cultural norms. Pragmatism permitted integration of both objective measurement and subjective interpretation. This allowed for a holistic examination of the retention factors of ground-level housekeeping staff in two distinct national contexts: Sri Lanka and Finland. Saunders et al. (2023) acknowledged that the pragmatist philosophy is an appropriate method that aligns with a range of techniques, qualitative and quantitative, and focuses on practical solutions and results.

Research approach

The study adopted a deductive approach. The identified main hypotheses and sub-hypotheses were tested. In other words, recognized theory/concept moves toward testing the ideas with gathered data. This aligns with Saunders et al. (2023), who acknowledged that the deductive approach is particularly suitable for theory falsification and verification.

Research method

The study adopted a mixed-methods design. Both quantitative and qualitative methods were integrated. The quantitative strand used survey questionnaires to identify statistically significant retention factors. The qualitative strand conducted semi-structured interviews to explore individual (management) perceptions and real-life experiences in greater depth. Creswell & Clark (2018) state that mixed methods are more appropriate when a single data source may be insufficient to understand a complex problem. The current study found difficulties, particularly from a quantitative perspective, due to a lower population and response rate in Finland. With the adoption

of qualitative interviews, the study enabled methodological triangulation, thereby increasing the validity of the findings. Likewise, understanding of organizational factors affecting retention is a complex process as it involves both quantifiable and subjective factors. Fetters et al. (2010) acknowledged that the mixed-method approach is a powerful tool in investigating complex processes. Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) recognized that mixed-method design can add insights and understanding that might be missed when only a single method is used. He further states that a mixed-method approach increases the generalizability of results and produces more complete knowledge necessary to inform theory and practice.

Research strategy

Two complementary strategies were adopted in this study: a survey and a multiple-case study. The survey strategy was employed to collect data from a large sample of housekeeping staff in two different contexts, Sri Lanka and Finland, facilitating comparative statistical analysis. The multiple-case study strategy was followed to select representative hotels from each country. This helped to understand the housekeeping staff's different perceptions and similarities in retention between the two cultural settings. Overall, the dual strategy allowed for both breadth and depth in understanding the factors influencing retention.

Time horizon

The study followed a cross-sectional time horizon, collecting data at a single point in time in each country, Sri Lanka and Finland. The cross-sectional design is appropriate for this study as it provides a snapshot of a situation and relationship in the present day (Wang & Cheng, 2020).

3.2. Case Firms, Population & Sample

Case firms

Eight 3-star hotels were selected for this study to evade bias, maximize transparency, and enhance reliability. Each country, Sri Lanka and Finland, is represented by four hotels. The study adopted a purposive sampling method, selecting 3-star hotels. Three-star hotels were selected based on rankings from major third-party platforms and independent hotel standings. Note that Finland has no official hotel star classification system, whereas Sri Lanka has a classification system managed by the SLTDA. However, in Sri Lanka, only a limited number of hotels have been officially categorized by SLTDA yet, and many hotels operate with third-party rankings and independent classifications. Since Finland does not have official rating systems and the majority of hotels in Sri Lanka were rated by third-party platforms or independently classified, this study selected 3-star hotels based on third-party and independent classification to ensure a fair selection process.

Selected four hotels for this study in Finland: Omena Hotel, Green Star Hotel, Astro Hotel, and Vallonia Hotel, Vaasa. However, out of those hotels, two are outsourcing housekeeping staff from an external company. Selected hotels in Sri Lanka include Hevan Seven Hotel, Kandy & Nuwaraeliya, Hotel Cassendra, Kandy, and Oakray Regency, Gatabe. Compared to Finland, 3-star hotels in Sri Lanka have more rooms, which represents a higher number of housekeeping staff, and thus the majority of staff are in-house. They follow staff outsourcing according to seasonality and train interns.

Population & Sample

The population of this study consisted of 120 ground-level housekeeping staff and 20 managers/supervisors employed in the selected hotel. The total population is 140. Of these, 120 staff members were considered the population for the quantitative study, with approximately 40 based in Finland and 80 based in Sri Lanka. The lower population in Finland reflects the structural difference between Sri Lanka and Finland's 3-star hotels. Finland's 3-star hotels are smaller in size than those in Sri Lanka and employ

fewer housekeeping staff. The sample included 100 participants for the quantitative study, while 10 managers were purposively selected for the qualitative phase of the study.

With the derived quantitative population, a total of 61 valid survey responses were obtained, including 20 from Finland and 41 from Sri Lanka. While the Finnish subsample is smaller in absolute terms, it represented approximately 50% of the total available population in the selected Finnish 3-star hotels. It was a proportionally strong coverage. Babbie (1973) and Kidder (1981) confirmed that a 50% response rate in a survey is an acceptable and sufficient rate, especially in social research (Nulty, 2008). Likewise, the Sri Lankan sample represented approximately 50% of the population. The same situation was reflected in interviews, such as a lower response rate from Finland. Out of the sample (10), the response rate was 6, 2 from Finland, and 4 from Sri Lanka. In this case, needs to be noted that an interviewed supervisor in Finland represented two hotels. The supervisor "X" is from an outsourced company and works as a supervisor for two hotels at the same time. Accordingly, it can be claimed that 3 hotels were represented in qualitative interviews out of 4 hotels in Finland. Hence, some managers in Finland refused to participate in interviews due to language barriers. Although the interview groups are not equal in size, proportional sampling enhanced comparability and supports the validity of cross-country analysis.

Sampling approaches differed between the two stands. For selecting housekeeping staff, simple random sampling was employed. It enables an equal chance for every person in the population. Simple random sampling is a probability method, whereas participants are chosen completely at random and are not biased. It is an appropriate method in quantitative research because it provides a fair and representative sample while reducing the influence of other factors (Noor et al., 2022). Snowball sampling was adopted in selecting managers because housekeeping supervisors, managers, and other executives have specific characteristics, knowledge, or experiences relevant to this study. Likewise, this population is relatively small and not easily accessible through

conventional sampling methods. Naderifar et al. (2017) stated that the snowball sampling method is appropriate for accessing hard-to-reach populations, particularly when the research requires participants with specialized characteristics or insights.

3.3. Data Collection

The quantitative phase involved a structured survey questionnaire (Appendix 03: Survey questionnaire-English, Appendix 04: Survey questionnaire-Sinhala, and Appendix 05: Survey questionnaire-Finnish). The instrument consists of sections on demographic information, organisational factors, and personal motivations for retention. The survey questionnaire has been distributed in a paper version, with the expectation of a higher response rate. Nulty (2008) justified that the response rate of paper surveys is higher than that of online surveys. Participants were ground-level housekeeping staff in both countries, Finland and Sri Lanka. The qualitative phase involved semi-structured interviews. The structured interview questionnaire is listed in Appendix 06. The time duration ranged from 10 to 20 minutes, but in some cases ran up to 30 minutes. It depended on the amount of information and interaction. Interviews were recorded with permission. Interviews were conducted in English in Finland and in Sri Lanka, both English and the Sinhala language, due to communication barriers. Participants included hotel managers, housekeeping managers, and supervisors. Interviews focused on staff remuneration, work stress culture, perceived supervisory support, training and development, retention, and challenges faced by housekeeping staff. The purpose of interviews is to gain an in-depth understanding of retention factors, complementing the survey. Ethical integrity was a key concern of this study. Privacy Note (Appendix 01) has been shared with all participants, and informed consent (Appendix 02) has been obtained. By signing informed consent, all participants assured that their participation was voluntary. Data has been collected and processed in accordance with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union, the Finnish Data Protection Act, and the Sri Lankan Personal Data Protection Act, No. 9 of 2022 (PDPA). Data were stored on secure computers and servers at the University of Vaasa. When reporting the results, subjects of interest and companies were

anonymised. Similarly, potentially identifiable parts were omitted from examples. In all communications, cultural sensitivity is observed, particularly during interviews, to ensure that questions are appropriate for both Sri Lankan and Finnish contexts.

3.4. Measures

Following validated measurement instruments used with the quantitative phase to examine the influence of remuneration & rewards, training & development, work–life balance, supervisory support, and work stress towards employee retention. Minor wording changes were made to fit the hotel context in Sri Lanka and Finland.

Remuneration & Rewards

Employee perceptions of remuneration & rewards were measured using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), adapted from Presbitero et al. (2016). The construct was measured using three items, including “rewards and recognition I receive from this job are attractive”, “I am satisfied with the income I receive”, and “I am satisfied with the benefits I receive”.

Training & Development

Perceptions of training & development opportunities were measured using the 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), adapted from Presbitero et al. (2016). Three items were included: “When people start new jobs here, they are given enough guidance and training.”, “There is a commitment to ongoing training and development of staff.”, and “The training and development I’ve received have improved my performance.”

Work–Life Balance.

Work–life balance was measured using the 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), adapted from Presbitero et al. (2016), which captures employees’ ability to balance work and personal responsibilities. Three items were listed

in the questionnaire. For example, sample item, “I can be involved in both work and non-work-related activities”.

Supervisory Support

Supervisory support was measured using three items derived from Presbitero et al. (2016) and Zhu et al. (2025). The 5-point Likert scale was used, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Sample item, “Supervisors are protective of and generous to loyal workers”.

Work Stress

Work stress was assessed using the 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), adapted from Asier et al. (2025). The scale consists of three questions, such as “I find it difficult to do my job because of conflicting demands.”, “I feel uncertain about the exact scope of my duties and responsibilities at work.”, and “Personality conflicts or strained relationships interfere with my ability to get quality work done.”

Employee Retention

The dependent variable, employee retention, was operationalized through employees’ intention to remain with the organization. A 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), adapted from Presbitero et al. (2016). Three items were used, including “I am likely to still be working in this organisation in 2 years”, “I would like to still be working in this organisation in 5 years”, and “I can see a future for me in this organisation”.

From a qualitative perspective, the structured interview questions were developed based on the constructs measured in the survey instrument. The interview aimed to explore the measures included in the survey questionnaire. Hence, the interview allowed a deep analysis of measures, permitting participants to elaborate on their experiences and provide contextual explanations. The interview questionnaire was

guided, piloted, and reviewed by experts to ensure clarity and alignment with the research objectives.

3.5. Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analysed using SPSS software. First, the quantitative phase was summarized by descriptive statistics. This helped to summarise the dataset and provide an overview of the distribution of responses. Accordingly, charts and tables were presented. Similarly, Mean and Standard Deviation were examined for each factor at the general model and separately for both countries. This allowed an initial understanding of trends and variations across the two samples. Secondly, inferential analysis was conducted to test hypotheses. Pearson correlation analysis was employed to examine the relationship between organizational factors (IVs) and employee retention (DV), at both general and contextual levels. Following, a regression analysis was conducted to examine how strongly each factor could predict staff retention. An ANOVA test was conducted to determine whether there were significant differences among the groups, with particular attention to comparisons between the two contexts. Regression coefficient analysis was employed in line with the general model and the country-specific models to understand the most influential variable influencing employee retention.

Qualitative data were analysed using the thematic analysis introduced by Braun and Clarke (2006). The method consists of a six-step framework: familiarisation with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the report (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Byrne (2021) noted that thematic analysis offers a systematic and rigorous technique for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns within qualitative data. The analysis started with familiarisation with the data. All interview recordings were listened to multiple times to gain an in-depth understanding of the content. The initial codes were then generated manually, giving descriptive labels to important parts of the text. In this study, manual coding is preferred as it allows the researcher to engage closely with the data and notice

small details that may be missed by automated software. Nelson et al. (2021) noted that automated coding methods, such as SML, can partially do what humans do, but humans are essential for accurate qualitative analysis. Accordingly, an open coding approach was adopted, allowing the data to reveal first-order concepts, which represent participants' own words and expressions. Thus, Blair (2015) argued that neither open coding nor template coding was definitely better. These first-order concepts were then examined and grouped into second-order themes, reflecting patterns, similarities, or relationships identified by the researcher. Then, the second-order themes were aggregated into new forms of exploitation and exploration (Key themes), establishing a hierarchical data structure that systematically links raw data to the study's key findings. Themes were further reviewed and refined to ensure that they accurately reflect the data and are distinct from one another. Each theme was defined and named, highlighting its relevance to the research objectives. All interviews were transcribed verbatim. Expecting better readability, minor grammatical corrections have been made in the quoted text without altering the meaning. Finally, the findings were reported systematically, with illustrative quotes from participants included to support the themes and demonstrate how the data structure connects raw participant statements to the overarching dimensions (Appendix 07: Qualitative Data Analysis).

3.6. The Assessment of the Quality Data

Assessing the quality of data is important in research because it is the foundation for trustworthy results. The assessment method in quality of data varies between qualitative and quantitative research due to the nature of the data. Since this study adopted a mixed-methods design, data quality was tested using diverse techniques and ultimately strengthened through triangulation. Gibbert et al. (2008) acknowledged that in the positivist tradition, four main criteria commonly used to assess the rigor of field research include internal validity, construct validity, external validity, and reliability.

Internal validity

The conceptual framework is guided by theories such as Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, Social Exchange Theory, and Job Demand Theory, which provide a lens for examining the factors affecting employee retention. After analyzing the data, the findings were interpreted using these theories to ensure that they are credible and logical. Use of multiple theories strengthened the study's validity by demonstrating that the results are reliable, theory-based, and accurately reflect the relationships found in the data. Moreover, in terms of the quantitative phase, the conceptual framework guided the development of the questionnaire. The relationships between the variables were analyzed statistically to ensure that the patterns observed were logical and consistent with the research questions. In the qualitative phase, thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) was adopted to analyze interview data. Thus, findings were interpreted in light of the conceptual framework, ensuring patterns and relationships were logically consistent.

Construct Validity

In the quantitative phase, the questionnaire items were adapted from validated instruments (Presbitero et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2025; Asier et al., 2025). Instrument's content validity verified by academics and industry experts, and criterion validity was checked using actual retention and turnover data. Hence, the pilot testing and reliability testing (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.834) further assured construct validity. In the qualitative phase, the data were collected through semi-structured interviews with managers and supervisors across countries. A transparent coding and systematic data analysis ensured alignment with research objectives. A transparent approach employed from participant quotes → codes → themes → overarching dimensions. Member checks were conducted to enhance trustworthiness. Also, the study triangulated by collecting and analyzing qualitative and quantitative data, which strengthened the construct validity of the findings.

External Validity

From a quantitative perspective, sample selection across Finland and Sri Lanka allows comparisons and supports theoretical generalization. In the qualitative phase, cases were selected purposefully through so-called theoretical sampling to provide contextually rich insights, and contextual information was provided to support analytical generalization.

Reliability

In the quantitative phase, the questionnaire process, scoring, and data entry were consistent and standardized. Reliability was confirmed using Cronbach's alpha and pilot testing. From the qualitative perspective, interviews were transcribed verbatim, and coding was performed systematically and documented. Clear interview protocols were followed consistently for all participants, and detailed reporting was provided to ensure dependability and transparency.

4. Findings

This chapter illustrates the findings of both quantitative and qualitative studies. The first section presents the quantitative results, including reliability checks, descriptive analysis, and inferential analysis. The second section demonstrates quantitative findings, including the coding process, developed sub-themes, key themes, and a summary. The third section reflects quantitative and qualitative triangulation.

4.1. Quantitative Analysis

Quantitative analysis consists of two parts: descriptive and inferential analysis, which illustrate the following. A reliability test was conducted to assess the internal consistency of six items, with a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.834. This is an accepted value, as it exceeds 0.70. This reveals that the items have greater internal consistency and reliably measure the same underlying construct. Taber (2018) noted that a value of 0.70 or over is a sufficient measure of reliability or internal consistency of an instrument.

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.834	6

Figure 3. Reliability Statistics (Cronbach's Alpha Value)

4.1.1. Descriptive Analysis

Figure 04 shows the country representation of respondents. Out of the total 61 respondents, 20 (33%) were from Finland and 41 (67%) from Sri Lanka. Finland indicates a lower respondent rate compared to Sri Lanka. This may be because 3-star hotels in Finland are smaller than those in Sri Lanka, and accordingly represent fewer staff.

Figure 4. Employee Representation by Countries

Table 01 illustrates the gender distribution among the respondents. Out of the total 61 ground-level housekeeping staff, 38 were male, 21 female, and 2 others. This suggests that the majority of ground-level housekeeping staff are male. However, in country-specific contexts, it varies.

Table 1. Employee Representation by Gender

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	38	62.3	62.3	62.3
	Female	21	34.4	34.4	96.7
	Other	2	3.3	3.3	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

Figure 05 shows the gender representation of employees in Finland; the majority of housekeeping staff are female, 13 out of 20. Out of the total respondents, 5 are males and 2 are others. This suggests that the Finnish context signifies gender diversity in work practices.

Figure 5. Employee Representation by Gender: Finland

Figure 6 showcases the gender diversity in Sri Lanka. Out of 41 total respondents, 33 are male. This indicates cultural reflection. Males have been given priority for work and earn income for their families, whereas women often stay at home and look after the family. Equally, this sample only exemplifies males and females, but not other genders. This examines the implementation of diversity, equity, and inclusion in the Sri Lankan hospitality context.

Figure 6. Employee Representation by Gender: Sri Lanka

Table 02 shows the type of employment of respondents. Out of the total number of ground-level housekeeping staff, 59% are full-time employees and 41% are part-time employees. This suggests that the hospitality industry is populated with both full-time

and part-time workers due to its nature. The hospitality industry is often based on seasonality, with 24-hour operation, and therefore, both part-time and full-time employees are equally important for effective operations.

Table 2. Employee Representation by Type of Employment

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Full_time	36	59.0	59.0	59.0
	Part_time	25	41.0	41.0	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

Figure 07 shows the distribution of employment types in Finland. The majority of respondents work as part-timers, 75%, which may be due to seasonality, cultural settings, and consideration of work-life balance. Likewise, this may be because of the low occupancy rate among 3-star hotels in Finland.

Figure 7. Employee Representation by Type of Employment: Finland

Figure 08 demonstrates the distribution of full-time and part-time employment in Sri Lanka. The distribution pattern completely opposes Finland. The majority of employees are full-timers, approximately 75%. This may be because the hospitality industry in Sri Lanka is one of the largest key economic drivers, and therefore, many employees are recruited as full-time. Likewise, seasonality has a minimal effect on the Sri Lankan hospitality industry, so it operates with peaks and needs more full-time workers.

Figure 8. Employee Representation by Type of Employment: Sri Lanka

Table 03 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation for each variable. Results show a Mean value for independent variables between 2.80 and 3.62. This reveals that the housekeeping staff expressed moderate acceptance of statements. Training & development resulted in the highest Mean of 3.60 (SD: 1.40). This suggests that staff seem to perceive training opportunities as fairly satisfactory. Conversely, Work Stress obtained the lowest mean (M = 2.80, SD = 1.33), signifying that those employees experienced a comparatively higher level of stress. Likewise, retention (dependent variable) was recorded with a mean of 3.36 (SD: 1.33). This indicates staff demonstrated a moderate tendency to retain. The Standard Deviation recorded among variables between 1.3 and 1.4 reveals that some staff members see factors positively, while others do not.

Table 3. Mean & Std. Deviation of Variables

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Remuneration & Rewards	61	1.00	5.00	3.2623	1.35962
Training & Development	61	1.00	5.00	3.6066	1.41095
Work-life Balance	61	1.00	5.00	3.3716	1.40515
Supervisory Support	61	1.00	5.00	3.5738	1.30686
Work Stress	61	1.00	5.00	2.8033	1.33802
Retention	61	1.00	5.00	3.3661	1.33847
Valid N (listwise)	61				

As illustrated in Table 04, Finland recorded the highest Mean values among remuneration & rewards (4.21), training and development (4.48), work-life balance (4.45), and supervisory support (4.43). This emphasizes that the housekeeping staff are satisfied with pay and rewards, receive acceptable training, execute better work-life balance, and have a higher level of supervisory support. However, work stress remains at a moderate level (2.65). Likewise, staff's retention intention also remains high, with a Mean value noted as 4.25. Moreover, lower Std. Deviation indicates that the staff responses are more alike. In Sri Lanka, a lower mean was recorded with remuneration & rewards of 2.80. This showcases employees' lower satisfaction. Work-life balance was recorded with a lower Mean value of 2.85. Work stress (2.78) is comparatively higher than in Finland. However, moderate satisfaction was recorded with training & development (3.18) and supervisory support (3.15). Retention was reported with a mean of 2.93, significantly lower than in Finland, suggesting a lower intention to stay. Likewise, higher standard deviations reveal a greater variance in individual responses.

Table 4. Comparison of Mean & Std. Deviation between Finland & Sri Lanka

		Descriptive Statistics				
Country		N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Finland	Remuneration & Rewards	20	2.33	5.00	4.2167	.71144
	Training & Development	20	3.00	5.00	4.4833	.53503
	Work-life Balance	20	3.67	5.00	4.4500	.42268
	Supervisory Support	20	2.67	5.00	4.4333	.58340
	Work Stress	20	1.00	5.00	2.6500	1.16215
	Retention	20	1.67	5.00	4.2500	.76376
	Valid N (listwise)	20				
Sri_Lanka	Remuneration & Rewards	41	1.00	5.00	2.7967	1.36194
	Training & Development	41	1.00	5.00	3.1789	1.50941
	Work-life Balance	41	1.00	5.00	2.8455	1.41833
	Supervisory Support	41	1.00	5.00	3.1545	1.36035
	Work Stress	41	1.00	5.00	2.8780	1.42352
	Retention	41	1.00	5.00	2.9350	1.35240
	Valid N (listwise)	41				

4.1.2. Inferential Analysis

Table 05 illustrates the Pearson Correlation analysis. “Correlation is a measure of a monotonic association between two variables” (Schober et al., 2018). Analysis indicates the relationship between organizational factors and retention. The results showcase that the remuneration & rewards ($r = .713$, $p < .01$), training & development ($r = .799$, $p < .01$), work-life balance ($r = .763$, $p < .01$), and supervisory support ($r = .770$, $p < .01$) are all positively and significantly core related to retention. In other words, when employees receive decent pay, better training opportunities, a good work-life balance, and better supervisory support, they are more likely to remain. The work stress, recorded a value of $r = -.249$, indicates a negative relationship with retention. This suggests that a higher level of stress may slightly contribute to negative retention.

Table 5. Pearson Correlation Analysis

		Correlations					
		Remuneratio n & Rewards	Training & Development	Work-life Balance	Supervisory Support	Work Stress	Retention
Remuneration & Rewards	Pearson Correlation	1	.756**	.792**	.882**	-.219	.713**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	.091	<.001
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61
Training & Development	Pearson Correlation	.756**	1	.806**	.861**	-.276*	.799**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001	.031	<.001
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61
Work-life Balance	Pearson Correlation	.792**	.806**	1	.859**	-.244	.763**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		<.001	.058	<.001
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61
Supervisory Support	Pearson Correlation	.882**	.861**	.859**	1	-.247	.770**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001		.055	<.001
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61
Work Stress	Pearson Correlation	-.219	-.276*	-.244	-.247	1	-.249
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.091	.031	.058	.055		.053
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61
Retention	Pearson Correlation	.713**	.799**	.763**	.770**	-.249	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	.053	
	N	61	61	61	61	61	61

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 06 demonstrates the comparison of Pearson Correlations between Finland & Sri Lanka. In Finland, remuneration & rewards ($r = .595$, $p < .01$), training & development ($r = .476$, $p < .05$), and work-life balance ($r = .485$, $p < .05$) were positively and significantly correlated. However, supervisory support ($r = .348$, $p > .05$) and work stress ($r = .361$, $p > .05$) were not significantly correlated.

> .05) did not show significant relationships with retention. In contrast, Sri Lanka indicates a strong positive correlation among retention and remuneration, training and development, work-life balance, and supervisory support ($r = .632, p < .01$), ($r = .781, p < .01$), ($r = .714, p < .01$), and ($r = .751, p < .01$), respectively. The relationship between work stress and retention has a significant negative correlation r value of $-.374, p < .05$.

Table 6. Comparison of Pearson Correlation in Finland and Sri Lanka

Country		Correlations						
			Remuneratio n & Rewards	Training & Development	Work-life Balance	Supervisory Support	Work Stress	Retention
Finland	Remuneration & Rewards	Pearson Correlation	1	.770**	.320	.805**	.217	.595**
		Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	.169	<.001	.359	.006
		N	20	20	20	20	20	20
	Training & Development	Pearson Correlation	.770**	1	.410	.774**	.324	.476*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		.073	<.001	.163	.034
		N	20	20	20	20	20	20
	Work-life Balance	Pearson Correlation	.320	.410	1	.235	-.055	.485*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.169	.073		.319	.817	.030
		N	20	20	20	20	20	20
	Supervisory Support	Pearson Correlation	.805**	.774**	.235	1	.201	.348
		Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	.319		.396	.133
		N	20	20	20	20	20	20
	Work Stress	Pearson Correlation	.217	.324	-.055	.201	1	.361
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.359	.163	.817	.396		.118
		N	20	20	20	20	20	20
	Retention	Pearson Correlation	.595**	.476*	.485*	.348	.361	1
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	.034	.030	.133	.118	
		N	20	20	20	20	20	20
Sri_Lanka	Remuneration & Rewards	Pearson Correlation	1	.688**	.756**	.854**	-.295	.632**
		Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	.061	<.001
		N	41	41	41	41	41	41
	Training & Development	Pearson Correlation	.688**	1	.771**	.830**	-.362*	.781**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001	.020	<.001
		N	41	41	41	41	41	41
	Work-life Balance	Pearson Correlation	.756**	.771**	1	.855**	-.274	.714**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		<.001	.083	<.001
		N	41	41	41	41	41	41
	Supervisory Support	Pearson Correlation	.854**	.830**	.855**	1	-.317*	.751**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001		.043	<.001
		N	41	41	41	41	41	41
	Work Stress	Pearson Correlation	-.295	-.362*	-.274	-.317*	1	-.374*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.061	.020	.083	.043		.016
		N	41	41	41	41	41	41
	Retention	Pearson Correlation	.632**	.781**	.714**	.751**	-.374*	1
		Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	.016	
		N	41	41	41	41	41	41

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Figure 09 reveals the model summary. This indicates how well the overall model explains the relationship between variables. A higher R value of 0.828 indicates a strong relationship between the predictors and retention. The model recorded an R^2 of 0.686, signifying that 68.6% of the variation in retention. In other words, 68.6% of the changes in the dependent variable are explained by the model, which is accepted by the perspective of social science research. Koirala (2025) noted that an R-Square value greater than 0.50 indicates that the model effectively determines the relationship. Likewise, the same has been justified by Ozili (2023). The adjusted R^2 value of 0.658 suggests that the model explains about 66% of the variation in the outcome and performs fairly well in representing the data. A Standard Error of the Estimate, recorded as 0.783, suggests, on average, the model-predicted retention scores differ from the actual scores by 0.78 points.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.828 ^a	.686	.658	.78286

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Stress, Remuneration & Rewards, Training & Development, Work-life Balance, Supervisory Support

Figure 9. Regression Model

Table 07 figures the ANOVA results. The ANOVA test determines whether an effect, factor, or model is significant (Brereton, 2018). The results confirm that the overall regression model is a good fit. $F(5,55) = 24.078$, $p < .001$, indicates that the combination of five independent variables, remuneration & rewards, training & development, work-life balance, supervisory balance, and work stress, has a significant effect on employee retention (statistically significant). Sureiman and Mangera (2020) stated that a p-value smaller than the significance level provides sufficient evidence that the predictor variables collectively improve the model's explanatory power. The model explains 68.6% of the changes in staff retention ($R^2 = 0.686$), which justifies a strong predictive capacity. However, the remaining 31.4% other factors not included in the given model. In a regression analysis, a residual is the difference between the actual value and the model's

predicted value (Lawrence & Kate, 2015). In the present study, the residual value is recorded as 33.708, indicating that the model unexplained some variance in staff retention.

Table 7. ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	73.782	5	14.756	24.078	<.001 ^b
	Residual	33.708	55	.613		
	Total	107.490	60			

a. Dependent Variable: Retention

b. Predictors: (Constant), Work Stress, Remuneration & Rewards, Training & Development, Work-life Balance, Supervisory Support

Table 08 presents the Regression Coefficient Analysis (Main model). Coefficient analysis identifies how each independent variables significantly contribute to predicting the dependent variable (Owad et al., 2020). Training & development significantly predicted retention: $\beta = 0.456$, $p = .005$. Means, H2 supported. In practice, this reveals that employees who receive training & development are more likely to remain in their current employment. Moreover, Leo and Sardanelli (2020) noted that using the conventional $p < 0.05$ threshold alone may not be enough. They recommended reporting actual p-values and, when appropriate, using stricter criteria. Accordingly, the present study follows the same. Remuneration & rewards, work stress, and supervisory support were not significant predictors (H1, H4, H5 = not supported). The stress shows a small negative effect, but it is not substantial. However, work-life balance (H3) indicates a slight positive effect, yet it is not statistically significant (directionally supported).

Table 8. Coefficient Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.492	.420		1.172	.246
	Remuneration & Rewards	.113	.160	.115	.709	.482
	Training & Development	.432	.147	.456	2.946	.005
	Work-life Balance	.241	.147	.253	1.639	.107
	Supervisory Support	.055	.225	.054	.244	.808
	Work Stress	-.023	.079	-.023	-.288	.775

a. Dependent Variable: Retention

Table 09 illustrates the Regression Coefficient Analysis for Finland. Remuneration & rewards recorded as $\beta = 0.747$, $p = .034$, indicate it is a significant positive predictor. In other words, better perceived pay and rewards lead to a higher level of staff retention in Finland. Hence, this supports H1a. Other independent variables, such as training & development, work-life balance, supervisory support, and work stress were not significant. In other words, they do not significantly predict retention in Finland. Accordingly, H2a, H3a, H4a, and H5a were not supported. However, the work-life balance “p” value was recorded as 0.072, suggesting a marginally positive, but not statistically significant.

Table 9. Coefficient Analysis: Finland

		Coefficients ^{a,b}				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	-.202	1.621		-.125	.903
	Remuneration & Rewards	.802	.342	.747	2.348	.034
	Training & Development	-.163	.471	-.114	-.347	.734
	Work-life Balance	.696	.358	.385	1.947	.072
	Supervisory Support	-.419	.426	-.320	-.983	.342
	Work Stress	.211	.124	.321	1.704	.110

a. Country = Finland

b. Dependent Variable: Retention

Table 10 exemplifies the Regression Coefficient Analysis for Sri Lanka. Among all predictors, training & development is the significant predictor of retention in Sri Lanka ($\beta = 0.440$, $p = .023$). This supports H2b. Other variables, including remuneration & rewards, work-life balance, supervisory support, and work stress, were not significant in retention. Though stress had a small negative effect, it was not significant. Accordingly, H1b, H3b, H4b, and H5b were not supported. This suggests that training & development is the most critical factor in Sri Lanka, among others, in retention.

Table 10. Coefficient Analysis: Sri Lanka

		Coefficients ^{a,b}				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.850	.529		1.609	.117
	Remuneration & Rewards	-.027	.190	-.027	-.142	.888
	Training & Development	.394	.166	.440	2.372	.023
	Work-life Balance	.161	.187	.169	.864	.394
	Supervisory Support	.231	.271	.233	.853	.400
	Work Stress	-.097	.101	-.102	-.966	.341

a. Country = Sri_Lanka

b. Dependent Variable: Retention

4.1.3. Key Findings & Summary

The majority of housekeeping staff consists of males. In Finland, the majority is represented by females, whereas in Sri Lanka, the opposite. This may be due to different cultural settings. In a general perspective, the majority of employees were employed full-time. In a contextual view, the majority of employees work part-time in Finland and full-time in Sri Lanka. In the main model, the Mean value of independent variables was recorded between 2.80 and 3.62, revealing that staff expressed moderate acceptance of statements. The retention was recorded as a Mean of 3.36 (SD:1.33), indicating a moderate tendency to retain. In contrast, Finland alone recorded higher Mean values among remuneration & rewards, training & development, work-life balance, and supervisory support. Work stress remained at a moderate level, while retention value remained high. In Sri Lanka, a lower Mean was recorded with remuneration & rewards, showcasing low satisfaction with pay. Likewise, work-life balance and work stress were recorded with a lower Mean value. A moderate satisfaction was recorded in training & development and supervisory support. Retention was reported with a mean of 2.93, significantly lower than in Finland, suggesting a lower intention to stay.

Person correlations recorded as remuneration and rewards ($r = .713$, $p < .01$), training and development ($r = .799$, $p < .01$), work-life balance ($r = .763$, $p < .01$), and supervisory support ($r = .770$, $p < .01$) are all positively and significantly core related to retention.

Work stress has a negative relationship with retention. In the country context, the majority of organizational factors were significantly correlated with retention in Finland. However, supervisory support and work stress did not show significant relationships with retention. Sri Lanka indicated a strong positive correlation among retention and remuneration, training and development, work-life balance, and supervisory support, while work stress showed a significant negative correlation. The regression model indicated a strong association between the predictors and employee: $R = 0.828$. The model explains 68.6% of the variance in retention ($R^2 = 0.686$) with a standard error of estimate of 0.78. ANOVA $F(5,55) = 24.078$, $p < .001$ indicated the overall model was statistically significant. The remaining 31.4% of variance is unexplained by the model and may reflect other factors, measurement error, or random variation

Regression analysis (Main model) identified training & development as a significant predictor of retention ($\beta = 0.456$, $p = .005$), supporting H2. Remuneration & rewards, work-life balance, work stress, and supervisory support were not recognised as significant predictors (H1, H3, H4, H5 not supported): See table 11. Examined multiple regression analysis (Table 12) found that the remuneration & rewards as a significant predictor of retention ($\beta = 0.747$, $p = .034$) in Finland, supporting H1a, while in Sri Lanka, training & development was the only significant predictor of retention ($\beta = 0.440$, $p = .023$), supporting H2b. These findings indicate that employees' retention factors are shaped by contextual factors.

Table 11. Summary of Main Hypotheses

Main Hypotheses	Result	Interpreation
H1: Remuneration & Rewards	Not supported	Even though the effect is positive, in this model, remuneration & rewards do not significantly predict retention.
H2: Training & Development	Supported (statistically significant)	Shows a strong, significant effect on retention.

H3: Work-life Balance	Directionally supported, but not significant	Not statistically confirmed, but a positive direction suggests a potential effect
H4: Supervisory Support	Not supported	Non-statistically significant effect on retention
H5: Work Stress	Not supported	Non-statistically significant effect on retention

Table 12. Summary of Sub-hypotheses

Sub-hypotheses	Result	Interpretation
H1a Remuneration & Rewards (Finland)	Supported, statistically significant	Better pay and rewards value Finnish employees for retention
H1b Remuneration & Rewards (Sri Lanka)	Not supported, not significant	Better pay and rewards do not significantly affect retention in the Sri Lankan context
H2a Training & Development (Finland)	Not supported, not significant	Training does not significantly affect retention in Finland
H2b Training & Development (Sri Lanka)	Supported, statistically significant	Training & development is a significant predictor of retention in Sri Lanka
H3a Work-life Balance (Finland)	Marginally supported, not statistically significant	It is somewhat positive, but not significantly
H3b Work-life Balance (Sri Lanka)	Not supported, not significant	It is not a significant factor in the Sri Lankan context
H4a Supervisory Support (Finland)	Not supported, not significant	It does not have a significant effect on retention
H4b Supervisory Support (Sri Lanka)	Not supported, not significant	It does not have a significant effect on retention
H5a Work Stress (Finland)	Not supported, not significant	Direction of effect in Sri Lanka aligns with expectations (negative), but is not statistically significant
H5b Work Stress (Finland)	Not supported, not significant	A minor, non-significant positive effect was found.

4.2. Qualitative Analysis

Six key themes were identified using the thematic analysis introduced by Braun and Clarke (2006), including remuneration & rewards, training & development, work stress, work-life balance, supervisory support, and retention. Each theme was developed from two sub-themes, which were identified through the coding process. Six participants were interviewed.

4.2.1 Theme 1: Remuneration & Rewards

Sub-theme 1: Financial motivation

Codes: Salary satisfaction & Fair pay

The findings reveal that the perception of fair pay is varied between Finland and Sri Lanka. In Finland, staff salaries are found to be fair and do not show a positive impact on turnover intentions. One of the Finnish managers mentioned:

“It is fair and satisfactory, as I hear from my employees. We do not have any staff turnover issues; they even ask for more working hours” (Interviewee 1).

Likewise, another manager stated, *“I am happy”* (Interviewee 3) with the current staff remuneration.

In Sri Lanka, remuneration appeared more central. For instance, a manager stated the positive impact of improved compensation:

“Compared to the past, at present staff (ex, interns) have been paid a fair salary, also a package including free accommodation and food.” (Interviewee 4).

Similarly, he further acknowledged the positive relationship between satisfactory remuneration and staff retention:

“If they are satisfied with salary & package, they are more likely to be retained” (Interviewee 4).

Yet another supervisor stressed dissatisfaction about the current staff remuneration:

“I am not 100% happy with the salary. Before one and a half years ago, staff had a good income, but with the new VAT%, staff are getting a lower service charge [...] service charge dropped by half.” (Interviewee 6)

He further argued that if staff are unable to cover their expenses aligned with remuneration, there is a higher possibility of leaving:

“If staff’s income does not match their expenses, they are more likely to leave”

(Interviewee 6)

These results confirm that salary satisfaction and fair pay are perceived as less critical in Finland. However, it is a strong domain in Sri Lanka, reflecting current economic pressure.

Sub-theme 2: Reward Strategies

Codes: Incentives & Bonuses

While Finnish managers stressed that they are happy and satisfied with rewards (*“I am happy.”* (Interviewee 3), in Sri Lanka, the reward mechanism is noted beyond the salary. For example, one manager highlighted:

“We reward whenever possible [...], recently we had International Housekeeping-week, we celebrated [...], our staff won a second place at one of the events, and after that we gave them another reward’ (Interviewee 2).

Similarly, one supervisor mentioned:

“If we can offer something like bonuses, staff are more likely to stay with their current job” (Interviewee 6)

Such practices suggest that incentives and bonuses act as staff retention strategies, though they may not hold equal weight in Sri Lanka and Finland. Participants in Finland placed less emphasis on formal reward strategies, reinforcing the idea that they may have a strong consideration of non-financial aspects, such as working culture and work-life balance, rather than rewards. However, rewards seem critical in the Sri Lankan context and indicate a positive relationship with staff retention.

Summary

The perception of fair pay varied between Finland and Sri Lanka. In Finland, staff salaries are standard fair, while in Sri Lanka, remuneration appears more central. Finnish management is satisfied with the rewards. Hence, it is critical in the Sri Lankan context.

Both contexts identified remuneration & rewards as a significant factor foremosting retention, though they have different weights.

4.2.2. Theme 2: Training & Development

Sub-theme 1: Skill Enhancement

Codes: Induction, Upskilling & Cross-training

All managers and supervisors from both countries, Finland and Sri Lanka, acknowledged the importance of skill development. Training in Finland is structured and formalised compared to Sri Lanka. A Finnish manager stated:

“When they start, they go through quite extensive training programs.”

“Also, we provide safety training very regularly.”

“Once every half year, we get a visit from a qualified trainer” (Interviewee 1).

Likewise, another manager highlighted that staff do not need further training, as they have become professional through long-term experience:

“No additional training needed, they work perfectly, now for a long time [...], now everybody knows what to do” (Interviewee 3)

In contrast, training in Sri Lanka is not structured or formal. Although training is less formal, it remains closely tied to employee retention. One manager explained;

“Whatever training is possible, we do give [...] when we feel candidates need further training [...], we put them on training, by that we are able to retain staff” (Interviewee 2)

This suggests the role of upskilling and cross-training not only enhances performance but also serves as a retention tool. However, one of the Sri Lankan managers argued, if a person is well-trained and skilled, there is a higher possibility of finding better opportunities.

“When they're fully trained [...], there is a high degree of chances they can get into a five-star hotel [...] or they can easily migrate” (Interviewee 2)

Sub-theme 2: Career Growth

Code: Extensive path & Personal development

Structured career development paths are emphasized in Finland, where in Sri Lanka, training was framed as a means of personal growth:

“We are providing quite an extensive path for their career development. They are receiving all the training they need” (Interviewee 1, Finland).

“We provide training for personal development. For example, when trainees come with basic knowledge, we help them to develop” (Interviewee 4, Sri Lanka).

Summary

Findings suggest that skill enhancement and career growth supported staff retention in Finland and Sri Lanka. However, this relationship has been challenged by migration opportunities and by the availability of better employment in Sri Lanka. Training in Finland is structured and formalised compared to Sri Lanka.

4.2.3. Theme 3: Work-life Balance

Sub-theme 1: Scheduling & Flexibility

Codes: Shift flexibility & Day-offs

Work-life balance has been well supported by formalized flexible scheduling and labour laws in Finland. Managers highlighted:

“Every shift has a maximum hour it can last; our employees get resting time according to the collective agreements” (Interviewee 1).

“We have only daytime work here... the manager is here, flexible” (Interviewee 3).

This emphasizes the Finnish rich working culture and how regulated flexible shifts allow employee to balance their work with personal life.

In contrast, Sri Lanka allows flexibility by providing day-offs and prioritizing staff requests. One manager stated:

“We are giving them needed day-offs monthly [...] when we compare to bigger hotels and small hotels all [...], even bigger hotels give six days off, we are giving them eight

days per month, also we have designed their shifts dynamically [...] for them to come up with their plans” (Interviewee 2).

Similarly, another manager highlighted the importance of day-offs in balancing family life:

“We provide day-offs on time, and provide request-offs, which leads to balancing family life” (Interviewee 4).

This indicates that day-offs act as a critical practice in achieving work-life balance of housekeeping staff, which in turn helps maximise staff retention.

Sub-theme 2: Personal Commitments

Codes: Family & Study Obligations

In Finland, personal commitments, like family obligations, are well addressed through flexible scheduling and regulations. However, personal commitments such as studies still affect employees' intention to resign. A manager stated:

“For example, if a person enrolls in the studies [...]; resign” (Interviewee 1)

In contrast, Sri Lanka displays higher personal commitments in terms of family obligations. This may be due to cultural settings. Some managers acknowledged:

“Due to family issues & personal problems, some staff were leaving jobs” (Interviewee 5)

“Personal commitments, like distance to home, available time to be involved with family, affect staff retention.” (Interviewee 4)

Likewise, another manager pinpointed strategies that they follow to overcome family obligations:

“I tell my staff to bring your family for a meal stay at my other properties [...], when we create a connection with that type of relationship with a family, it's easy for our team to concentrate on work.” (Interviewee 2)

These findings indicate the criticality of family obligations in Sri Lanka. Hence, managers identified fulfilling family obligations as a key driver in employee retention, and thereby, they take possible strategies to balance work and family obligations.

Summary

Together, flexible scheduling and personal commitments reflect work-life balance in both contexts in Finland and Sri Lanka. Finland follows structured scheduling to maximize work-life balance, as identified, which is a key driver of staff retention. Sri Lanka allows flexibility by providing day-offs and prioritizing staff requests. Although Sri Lanka followed strategies to sustain work-life balance, it still struggles to balance staff family obligations with work requirements.

4.2.4. Theme 4: Supervisory Support

Sub-theme 1: Recognition & Mentorship

Codes: Feedback & Guidance

In Finland, managers highlighted the importance of recognition by providing fair feedback. Fair feedback increases staff satisfaction. For instance, managers stated:

“Staff are satisfied when they are assessed in a justice way, and they are not being provided negative feedback, but also positive feedback” (Interviewee 1)

“I always try to say, [...] good job, example, make the bed nicely” [...] I tried to be nice.” (Interviewee 3)

Accordingly, it can be justified that recognition is a powerful mechanism that increases staff morale and satisfaction, which consequently leads to retention.

In contrast, Sri Lankan managers highlighted the importance of mentoring, rather than just providing feedback or guidance. For instance, managers highlighted:

“Rather than just providing feedback or guidance, if a supervisor can show and demonstrate actions by themselves, I believe it is a good way of practice, so that staff can capture and learn more.” (Interviewee 4)

“As I see, a supervisor is the person who inspires staff, and such should be leading by example [...]. If so, it is easy to guide the team.” (Interviewee 5)

Similarly, one manager explained how his mentorship helped staff to find better opportunities:

“My mentoring helped some staff to reach better opportunities, for example, now some are working in Hilton, Radisson, Dubai, and the UK. (Interviewee 4)

Results reveal that recognition and fair feedback were dominant in Finnish culture, whereas Sri Lanka preserved supervisory support by mentoring. Both countries equally recognised the importance of providing feedback and guidance, enhancing supervisory support.

Sub-theme 2: Leadership Behavior

Codes: Approachability & Problem-solving

All managers in both countries, Finland and Sri Lanka, acknowledged the significance of Leadership. Finnish managers highlighted that the leader should provide guidance, and also need to approach in practice by actively engaging. One manager stated:

“Supervisor is a leader and a good leader; for example, he not only provides theory and practice, but also actively participates in employees' everyday tasks.” (Interviewee 1)

Likewise, she further explained how she solved a problem in practice:

“We got a situation, because of personal reasons, a person couldn't do a certain shift, so not to reduce he/her hours, I offered shifts in other places” & “we are trying to observe each other and take care of our well-being” (Interviewee 1)

Similarly, another manager stated her leadership style in problem-solving:

“We do not have gossip like something [...], I will say something bothers me [...] I don't talk about behind” (Interviewee 3)

Findings indicate the importance of leadership, approach, and problem-solving in retaining employees. Yet, leadership style, approach, and problem-solving methods may vary person to person.

In contrast, Sri Lankan managers similarly acknowledged the importance of leadership in the hospitality context. According to them, supervisors' behaviour is directly associated with staff satisfaction and retention. For instance, managers stated:

“I believe the way a supervisor behaves directly affects staff satisfaction, for example, how you talk and engage.” (Interviewee 4)

“According to my knowledge, staff stay if the supervisor behaves well, such as their relationship is important [...], for example, if I leave one hotel for another, there are several staff who are willing to come with me” (Interviewee 5)

Likewise, one manager highlighted the involvement of management in solving a problem that a supervisor was unable to address:

“If a supervisor wants to say something to his staff, but if he feels sometimes that if I say, this one may be misunderstood, I can't get the work done, then we (management) just address that problem.” (Interviewee 2)

Summary

Findings reveal how recognition, mentoring, and leadership behaviors are important in terms of supervisory support. In Finnish culture, fair recognition and constructive guidance were emphasized, whereas in Sri Lanka, the importance of mentoring was emphasized beyond guidance. Both countries recognized leadership as a crucial element in supervisory support; thus, supervisory support is a key driver in employee retention.

4.2.5. Theme 5: Work Stress

Sub-theme 1: Workload & Physical Demands

Codes: Heavy workload, Quality, Early check-ins & Long shifts

Workload dominated as the central source for stress in both countries, Finland & Sri Lanka. But it depended on various reasons. In Finland, the heavy workload was reported during peak seasons. Similarly, quality maintenance further led to increased stress. One manager highlighted:

“Time is quite tight, especially during the summer season, and second, the quality standards that we have to follow” (Interviewee 1).

Likewise, another manager stated that staff are stressed due to more work and fewer employees:

“Some days we are really stressed because there is a lot of cleaning... sometimes we have fewer cleaners” (Interviewee 3).

In contrast, in Sri Lanka, workload pressures were tied to early/back-to-back check-ins and timing. Some managers highlighted:

“Early check-ins lead to workload and stress as it has limited time to clean a room”
(Interviewee 5).

“Housekeeping is hard work... we don’t have enough time to prepare rooms, also we cannot ask guests to leave, and similarly can’t satisfy those who are coming”
(Interviewee 6).

These findings indicate that workload in Finland is dominated by seasonality, whereas in Sri Lanka due to early check-ins and operational timing. Likewise, findings highlighted practical issues in housekeeping, such as how late check-outs and early arrivals affect operations and maximise work stress.

Sub-theme 2: Interpersonal Stress

Codes: Conflicts & Pressure

Interpersonal stress remains a significant element in both contexts in Finland and Sri Lanka. Though it may vary in terms of work culture, leadership, and personnel perception. Finnish managers follow open discussion to resolve conflicts and reduce interpersonal stress. One manager stated:

“Sometimes I talk to my boss, say: we really need more (staff)” and [...] she takes more”
(Interviewee 3)

In contrast, Sri Lankan managers advanced all possible strategies to decrease conflict and interpersonal stress. One manager highlighted:

“We have to understand them (staff), their expectation and requirements, say, if a person wants to take a leave for personal work, definitely we have to cater to that one, otherwise, he is going to work under pressure” (Interviewee 2)

This discloses how crucial personal stress in housekeeping operations and, thereby, management takes all possible strategies to reduce stress at the workplace, noting the significant relationship between work stress and employee retention.

Summary

Workload dominated as the central source for work stress in both contexts, for various reasons. In Finland, the heavy workload was reported during peak seasons and due to quality maintenance. In Sri Lanka, workload pressures were tied to early/late and back-to-back check-ins. Interpersonal stress was reported as a significant element in both contexts. Both countries implement possible strategies to address work stress, as it is one of the key factors to ensure employee retention.

4.2.6. Theme 6: Retention

Sub-theme 1: Staff Commitment

Codes: Loyalty & Intention to stay

Finland showcased a strong staff loyalty among the organization and an intention to stay. One manager stated:

“Actually, we don’t have any staff turnover.” (Interviewee 1)

Likewise, she further explained that she never had a problem with staff leaving because they found a better place, except for one situation, where a person wanted to enroll in studies:

“For example, if a person enrolls in the studies, this is the only reason faced (Resigned); not that someone changed the work because they found something better.” (Interviewee 1)

Similarly, another manager highlighted:

“We are like family here” (Interviewee 3)

In contrast, the Sri Lankan context demands fair salary, accommodation, and appropriate working conditions to retain. One manager stated:

“A good salary, accommodation, and work environment maximize staff retention and reduce staff leaving the job” (Interviewee 4)

Likewise, another manager argued that middle-aged staff are thoroughly demanding and depend on remuneration, whereas young staff demand new knowledge that they can enhance their development:

“I believe young people are more likely to stay if they receive new knowledge. But, when it comes to middle age, they are more dependent on salary.” (Interviewee 5)

Sub-theme 2: Organizational Factors

Codes: Culture & Environment

Both managers in Finland and Sri Lanka acknowledged the significance of working culture and environment in retaining staff. Similarly, the importance of satisfactory remuneration was highlighted. One Finnish manager stated:

“This is a very good company when it comes to working atmosphere” (Interviewee 1)

She further emphasized other organizational factors to be considered in employee retention:

“General work satisfaction, good work-life balance, satisfactory salary, and the possibility of development.” (Interviewee 1)

Likewise, another manager acknowledged the working culture:

“We go hang out twice a year.” (Interviewee 3)

In contrast, the Sri Lankan managers similarly acknowledged the importance of working culture, fair remuneration, and developing opportunities. However, a fair salary is crucial in the Sri Lankan context due to economic conditions. One manager highlighted:

“At present, remuneration is a highly considerable factor when a person chooses an employment, considering living costs, especially in Sri Lanka.” (Interviewee 4)

Likewise, another manager stated the importance of working culture, such as fair treatment and recognition:

“Example, if I have been treated unfairly [...], that kind of situation [...], even other factors met [...], there is a high degree of questionable retention.” (Interviewee 2)

Another manager emphasized the importance of opportunities for staff development in staff retention:

“I think staff are more interested in developing, so we need to show them how to reach their targets within a timeframe [...]. If we do so, I believe they will stay.” (Interviewee 5)

Summary

Finland demonstrated a strong staff loyalty and intention to stay. The Sri Lankan context emphasizes the need for fair salaries, accommodation, and proper working conditions to ensure retention. Both Finnish and Sri Lankan managers recognized working culture as a significant element in retaining staff. However, a fair salary holds greater significance in Sri Lanka due to economic conditions.

4.2.7. Key Findings & Summary

The perception of fair pay varied between Finland and Sri Lanka. In Finland, salaries were recognised as standard and fair, whereas remuneration appears more central in Sri Lanka. Finnish managers were satisfied with the pay and rewards, while it remained critical in Sri Lanka. Both contexts identified pay and rewards as a significant factor foremosting retention. Similarly, recognise the importance of training & development. However, the positive relationship between career development and retention has been challenged due to migration opportunities and the availability of better opportunities in Sri Lanka. Workload dominated as the central source for work stress in both contexts, for various reasons. Heavy work was reported during peak seasons and in accordance with quality maintenance in Finland. In Sri Lanka, workload pressures were tied to early/late and back-to-back check-ins. Likewise, interpersonal stress was reported in both contexts. Mutually, both contexts implement possible strategies to reduce work stress, as it is a critical factor in retention. Finland follows structured schedules to maximize work-life balance, whereas Sri Lanka aims to achieve work-life balance by offering required day-offs and prioritizing staff requests. Yet Sri Lanka struggles to balance staff family obligations with work requirements. Both countries equally recognised the importance of supervisory support in employee retention. As well, recognized the significance of leadership in supervisory support. Fair recognition and constructive guidance were highlighted with supervisor support in Finland. Sri Lanka highlighted mentoring beyond guidance. Finland showcased strong staff loyalty and

intention to stay. In contrast, Sri Lankan employees demand fair salaries, accommodation, and proper working conditions to ensure retention.

4.3. Quantitative & Qualitative Triangulation

The Mean value for independent variables, such as remuneration & rewards, training & development, work-life balance, supervisory support, and work stress, remained statistically between 2.80 and 3.62. This suggests that employees expressed moderate acceptance of statements, which was similarly justified by qualitative findings. The managers from both contexts noted that their staff receive fair pay, opportunities for career development, satisfactory work-life balance, adequate supervisory support, and moderate stress due to seasonality and late /early check-ins. Retention recorded a Mean of 3.36, indicating that staff have a moderate tendency to retain. This can be justified with the statements provided by Finnish managers; however, contradictions were observed with Sri Lankan managers, highlighting contextual variation. A comparison of the Mean value between two contexts found various results of acceptances. In the Finnish context, the Mean value recorded as remuneration & rewards (4.21), training & development (4.48), work-life balance (4.45), and supervisory support (4.43), which emphasized that the housekeeping staff are satisfied with pay and rewards, receiving acceptable training, experiencing better work-life balance, and receiving a higher level of supervisory support. This aligns with qualitative findings; Finnish managers stated that their staff are happy with pay, undertake a structured and extensive training process, receive days off, and have appropriate shift schedules and supervisory support, like fair recognition. The Mean value of work stress was 2.65, indicating that a moderate level of stress occurs in the workplace. Thus, this has also been justified by Finnish managers, who highlighted that staff experienced stress during peak season, while maintaining high-quality standards. Likewise, staff retention was recorded as the Mean value of 4.25, indicating a higher tendency towards retention. This can be justified by Finnish managers stating that they do not have any problem with employee turnover; rather, they demand more hours for work. In Sri Lanka, a lower Mean was recorded with

remuneration & rewards of 2.80, indicating low satisfaction with pay & rewards. However, the majority of managers in Sri Lanka stated that their staff have considerably fair remuneration and a rewarding system, including free meals, accommodation, and uniforms. This showcases a contradiction between quantitative results and qualitative insights. Hence, this can be similarly interpreted as a paradox between the management and staff views. Work-life balance was recorded as a Mean value of 2.85, and work stress (2.78), indicating that staff moderately accepted statements, whereas they were not fully happy with work-life balance and work stress. This is also validated by Sri Lankan managers, who said that they are still struggling to balance staff family obligations, and staff receive stress due to back-to-back guest arrivals and check-ins. Statistically, moderate satisfaction was recorded with training & development (Mean: 3.18) and supervisory support (Mean: 3.15). This corresponded with managers' declarations; the majority of them highlighted that staff receive training whenever possible and are provided mentoring beyond the guidance of a supervisor. Retention was reported with a Mean of 2.93, significantly lower than in Finland, suggesting a lower intention to stay. This is consistent with the qualitative findings and similarly with other quantitative findings. From a qualitative perspective, managers highlighted a higher possibility of staff leaving due to better opportunities available. From a quantitative stance, remuneration & rewards recorded the lowest Mean value, indicating dissatisfaction; therefore, employees are unlikely to retain.

Pearson's core relations was recorded as remuneration and rewards ($r = .713, p < .01$), training and development ($r = .799, p < .01$), work-life balance ($r = .763, p < .01$), and supervisory support ($r = .770, p < .01$) and work stress ($r = -0.249, p = 0.053$). Except for work stress, all other variables are positively and significantly correlated with retention. Work stress indicated a weak negative correlation with retention. These results corresponded with the insights obtained from the qualitative analysis. The managers highlighted that good pay and rewards, better training opportunities, appropriate work-life balance, and greater supervisory support maximize employee retention, and a higher level of work stress minimizes retention.

As an overall model, training & development significantly predicted retention: $\beta = 0.456$, $p = .005$, supported H2. This reveals that employees who receive better opportunities for training & development are more likely to remain in their current employment. Qualitative findings support the trend; however, the majority of managers highly emphasized the importance of better pay, among other themes, which were not identified as significant predictors in the quantitative regression model. It needs to be noted that qualitative findings are reported for each theme individually, whereas the quantitative regression analysis evaluates all predictors simultaneously within a single model. H1 (remuneration & rewards), H4 (supervisory support), and H5 (supervisory support) were not significant predictors in this statistical model, whereas H3 (work-life balance) indicated a slight positive effect, but not statistically significant (directionally supported), which moderately aligned with qualitative insights.

As per country-based regression analysis, remuneration & rewards were recorded as $\beta = 0.747$, $p = .034$, in Finland. This indicates a significant positive predictor of retention, supporting H1a. This is supported by Finnish managers who stated that their staff are happy with pay and rewards, and do not have turnover intentions. All other predictors were not significant and supported (H2a, H3a, H4a, and H5a). In the Sri Lankan context, among all predictors, training & development was the significant predictor of retention ($\beta = 0.440$, $p = .023$), which supported H2b. However, qualitative findings significantly emphasized the importance of better pay in retention rather than training & development due to critical economic conditions. Yet, the statistical model did not recognize remuneration & rewards, work-life balance, supervisory support, and work stress as significant predictors of retention in Sri Lanka. H1b, H3b, H4b, and H5b were not supported.

Overall, it can be concluded that the quantitative findings and qualitative insights aligned, yet a few contradictions were observed. These contradictions may have occurred due to the various views of managers and staff, or because the qualitative findings were reported for each theme individually, whereas quantitative regression

analysis evaluates all predictors simultaneously within a single model. All organizational factors remain important for staff retention, although only some emerge as significant in the model.

5. Discussion

The chapter consists of four sections. The first section illustrates the theoretical contribution. The second section discusses the managerial implications. The third section examines the limitations, and finally, the fourth section offers suggestions for future research.

5.1. Theoretical Contribution

This section is organized into four subtopics: theoretical positioning, interaction with existing theories, novel theoretical contributions, and a concluding summary.

5.1.1. Theoretical Positioning

This study is based on HRM and organizational behavior theories, including Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, Social Exchange Theory, and Job Demands–Resources Theory. These theories suggest that employee retention is shaped by a blend of motivation, relationships, organizational, and environmental factors. Thus, these collectively provide a multi-dimensional understanding of employee retention. However, most existing studies applied these theories, focusing on managerial employees, often in developed countries, while comparative analyses between developing and developed countries remain scarce. This has created a theoretical gap in understanding how these theories apply to ground-level staff in developed and developing countries, particularly with reference to housekeeping in 3-star hotels. To address this gap, the present study conducts a comparative analysis of employee retention in ground-level housekeeping staff at 3-star hotels between Finland and Sri Lanka. This comparative approach allows an examination of whether the theoretical relationships proposed by HRM and Organizational Behaviour (OB) frameworks hold across different socio-economic and cultural environments. The study particularly focuses on the influence of remuneration & rewards, training & development, work-life balance, supervisory support, and work stress.

5.1.2. Interaction with Existing Theories

As noted by Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959), remuneration is a hygiene factor, indicating that poor pay causes dissatisfaction and reduces retention; thus, better pay alone may not increase the employee's long-term commitment (Shinde, 2025). However, the current study found that remuneration & rewards were statistically significant only in Finland, which may appear inconsistent with Herzberg. This could be due to cultural or economic factors, where fair pay is closely tied to perceived motivation and engagement, suggesting that in certain contexts, hygiene factors may also indirectly influence commitment. Supporting this, Ozsoy (2019) found that the salary is a motivation factor, rather than merely a hygiene factor. In contrast, remuneration was recorded as insignificant in Sri Lanka, aligning more closely with Herzberg's original distinction, where low-wage employees may prioritize stability and skill development over monetary rewards alone. This shows that the relative importance of hygiene and motivator factors may vary across socio-economic and cultural contexts. Therefore, Herzberg's framework may require contextual adaptation on a global scale.

As explained by Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964), when employees feel that the organization cares for them and treats them fairly, they are more likely to reciprocate by increasing motivation, loyalty, commitment, and retention (Birtch et al., 2016). Training & development can be viewed as an organizational investment that, in return, expects loyalty, commitment, and retention from employees (Xuecheng et al., 2022). However, in this study, training & development emerged as a strong and significant predictor of retention in Sri Lanka but not in Finland. This may be because employees in developing countries, such as Sri Lanka, perceive training & development as an investment, whereas Finnish employees may view it as a standard entitlement. Therefore, this current study extends Social Exchange Theory, suggesting that employees perceive the value of organizational investments differently depending on their socioeconomic conditions and labor market expectations. Moreover, the study, "The Relevance of Personal and Cultural Values: The New Era Workplace Relationships: Is Social Exchange Theory Still Relevant?" (2019) found that cultural values or contextual

factors influence how employees perceive organisational investments (Chernyak-Hai & Rabenu, 2018). Likewise, Cropanzano and Mitchell (2005) emphasized that the employees' perceptions of desirable relations in the new workplace may be affected by personal and cultural values.

Following Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) Theory (2001), work stress is a demand factor; when it is not reinforced with adequate resources, such as support, training, and recognition, employees experience burnout and turnover (Galanakis & Tsitouri, 2022). Yet, this present study found that work stress was not a statistically significant predictor of retention in either Finland or Sri Lanka, although the trend was in the expected direction. This does not necessarily contradict the JD–R framework; rather, it may reflect contextual differences or the presence of buffering resources that mitigate the negative impact of stress on employee retention. Hence, some employees may take work stress as part of their jobs and normalize it, emphasizing the need for a nuanced interpretation of the JD-R Theory. In practice, employees do not always react to stress by leaving, and contextual factors matter. In some industries, stressors are accepted. Vetráková et al. (2019) provided empirical justification that stress is frequent and normal in the hospitality industry, and thus, that turnover causes are broader than stress alone. The study found that almost 49% of hotel employees experience stress several times a week, though the main reasons for leaving the job are: (1) low wages, (2) insufficient conditions of development and self-realization, (3) managers' work style, (4) poor working conditions, and (5) lack of free time.

5.1.3. Novel Theoretical Contribution

The current study provides a novel contribution to the cross-cultural application of retention theories. The study identified that HR theories have opposite effects in various countries or contexts. The study compared a developed country (Finland) and a developing country (Sri Lanka) using the same model, which is rare in existing studies. For instance, Huo (2019) examined employee retention solely within the United States,

and Aufa et al. (2023) investigated it only within Indonesia. In a general perspective, the study identified that training & development significantly predicted retention of ground-level housekeeping staff in 3-Star hotels, among other variables, remuneration & reward, work-life balance, supervisory support, and work stress. However, in a contextual perspective, the study found that remuneration and training do not have the same meaning in different cultures and income levels.

In Finland, remuneration & rewards were significantly positively related to retention (H1a supported), and other independent variables, such as training & development, work-life balance, supervisory support, and work stress were not significant (H2a, H3a, H4a, H5a not supported). In contrast, in Sri Lanka, among all predictors, training & development was the only significant predictor of retention (H2b supported), and others, remuneration & rewards, work-life balance, supervisory support, and work stress were not substantial in retention (H1b, H3b, H4b, H5b not supported). This is consistent with Hofstede's (2001) cultural dimensions theory, which posits that people's attitudes, behaviors, and responses to management practices are influenced by their culture and country. The present study confirms that the effectiveness of HR practices varies in different socioeconomic and cultural settings, highlighting that one-size-fits-all approaches to employee retention have limits. Hence, Wahyudi et al. (2023) noted that employee retention is a complex challenge with no single solution that works for everyone. Most classical theories assume that motivational drivers are globally applicable. The universalist assumption declares that the human motivation process is universal, such as Maslow's hierarchy of needs, Herzberg's theory, achievement motivation theory, equity theory, and expectancy theory (Luthans & Doh, 2012). However, the present study justifies that the meaning of HR practices depends on the specific contexts. Brewster (2007) found that HRM practices differ between Europe and the U.S., and HRM practices must consider context, socioeconomic, and cultural settings; there is no single model that works everywhere. Ghani et al. (2022) emphasized that the concept of employee retention is broad; many existing hospitality retention studies are limited to specific contexts and, accordingly, called for research

that considers diverse contexts, a gap that the present study addresses. Likewise, Han (2020) highlighted the importance of cross-cultural studies in the hospitality industry, and he further stated that factors predicting turnover work differently in different cultures. Moreover, it can be concluded that the present study introduced context as a theoretical lens by interacting with existing theories, particularly Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959), Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964), and Job Demands–Resources Theory (2001), all of which were addressed above.

As the present study found, remuneration & rewards are significant for Finnish employees. This may be due to high living costs, wage expectations, and recognition through non-monetary rewards. In 2024, Finland recorded a price level index for household final consumption of 124 (EU27 = 100), indicating that Finland's price levels for goods & services were about 24 % above the EU average (Statistics Norway, 2025). Davidson et al. (2011) acknowledged that housekeeping is a low-wage occupation and, therefore, Finnish employees may be more concerned about pay and rewards. Dharini and Premkumar (2025) observed that employees are more likely to feel a sense of belonging when organizations provide non-monetary incentives.

Training & development were significant for Sri Lankan employees because, in an emerging country like Sri Lanka, housekeeping staff often see their job as a starting point in the hospitality industry, and it is a pathway to career progress and better job opportunities, such as in higher-rated hotels or abroad. Thus, this has been confirmed by managers during interviews. Preko and Anyigba (2024) acknowledged that many ground-level jobs in the tourism and hospitality industry serve as initial starting points, and often, later employees move into higher-level roles. Equally, Sri Lankan employees may consider training & development as an investment in terms of job security. Akkermans et al. (2019) found that employees identify training & development as an investment, from both internal and external employability, such as career growth within the organization and outside, giving job security beyond their current workplace. In collectivist cultures like Sri Lanka's, employees often value education and skill

development as a way to contribute to their family, community, and as a mode of gaining social recognition, which is consistent with Hofstede's (2001) cultural dimensions theory. Also, many 3-star hotels in Sri Lanka offer similar pay packages; therefore, remuneration is not a strong differentiator, and what makes employees retain is the opportunities for learn and development. This is supported by the empirical study of Devi and Premaratne (2015), who found that financial compensation was not statistically significant in predicting employee motivation in the hotel sector; instead, the study found that career development is a significant factor in motivation and retaining employees.

Many existing studies in the hospitality industry have been conducted in departments like Food & Beverage and Front Office operations. For instance, Silva and Perera (2020) studied retention of food & beverage staff, and Streeter et al. (2021) studied front office staff. Nonetheless, this study focused on the housekeeping department, often neglected by academia. Saehya et al. (2023) highlighted that housekeeping is an invisible department and, as a result, it has not received attention from researchers. Likewise, this study focused on ground-level housekeeping employees, whereas many existing studies focus on the managerial level. For example, Hemdi and Rahim (2011) studied "the effect of psychological contract and affective commitment on turnover intentions of hotel managers", and Martins et al. (2025) studied "employee retention practices in the Portuguese hospitality industry," focusing on management professionals. Therefore, this study contributes new knowledge to the academic literature, particularly in the field of hospitality and tourism.

Many previous hospitality studies have been conducted based on high-end star-class hotels or with luxury hotels. 3-star hotels have often been mistreated in the research phenomenon. As evidenced by Streeter et al. (2021), who studied resorts & conventional hotels, and Kumar and Singh (2015) selected five-star hotels in Delhi. The 3-star hotels segment is a significant sector in the hospitality industry and the economy. Dogru et al. (2020) acknowledged that the midscale hotels make the highest

contribution to employment in the overall economy. Therefore, this study contributes novel insights to the hospitality literature, emphasizing the importance of the 3-star hotel sector.

The study partially responded to the call of Presbitero et al. (2016), “future research may consider using more objective measures of retention to ascertain whether employees do stay or not, and track which factors influence employee intention to leave the organization”. The actual data were considered in qualitative insights, such as employee turnover rate. Also, both quantitative and qualitative approaches provided a comprehensive and multi-dimensional understanding of employee retention.

Alike, this study is answered the call of Huo (2019), “future empirical research could shed light on determining the correlation between demographics such as ethnicity, age, gender, years of experience, and retention factors and defining and constructing the multiple regression analysis by identifying how the weight of each factor contributes to the reasons to stay in the same organization for a long period”. The current study conducted multiple regression analysis between Finland and Sri Lanka. Therefore, the study was able to understand how various ethnicity reflects among selected variables in retention.

In the same vein, this study answered the call of Andrade, Miller, and Westover (2020), “future research should address in more detail the impact pay has on job satisfaction for hotel housekeepers across countries”. The current study was conducted among housekeeping staff in different contexts, Finland and Sri Lanka, and remuneration was a key predictor. Therefore, it can be concluded that the study filled the empirical gap mentioned by Miller and Westover.

5.1.4. Summary

The study offers a novel contribution to the cross-cultural application of retention theories by addressing the neglected ground-level housekeeping staff in 3-star hotels. The study introduced a contextual lens to understand employee retention, highlighting that the motivational drivers vary among diverse socioeconomic and cultural backgrounds. The present study found that remuneration & rewards were statistically significant only in Finland, which appears inconsistent with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959). Likewise, training & development emerged as a strong and significant predictor of retention in Sri Lanka, whereas it does not in Finland. This extends Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964), suggesting that employees perceive the value of organisational investments differently depending on their socioeconomic conditions and labour market expectations. Equally, the study found that work stress was not a significant predictor of retention in either Finland or Sri Lanka, although the trend was in the expected direction. This does not necessarily contradict the JD–R framework; rather, it may reflect contextual differences or the presence of buffering resources that mitigate the negative impact of stress on employee retention. However, the present study is consistent with Hofstede's (2001) cultural dimensions theory, which advocates that people's attitudes, behaviours, and responses to management practices are influenced by their culture and country.

5.2. Managerial Implications

The findings of the current study provide significant guidelines and implications for hotel managers, housekeeping managers, and HR practitioners. However, as key retention factors vary between Sri Lanka and Finland, managers should apply strategies, particularly by understanding employee expectations, cultural values, and economic conditions.

Since the pay & rewards matter significantly for Finnish employees, management can use remuneration & rewards strategically. For example, management can introduce

performance-based bonuses and loyalty incentives aligned with staff years of service. Artz and Heywood (2025) noted that performance pay is increasingly used as a long-term retention tool, and it works well in small businesses, which aligns with the 3-star hotel segment. Similarly, management can offer non-monetary recognitions, such as selecting the employee of the month. Aligned with those strategies, management can use a forced distribution rating system (FDRS). Moon et al. (2016) highlighted that FDRS increases employees' performance while helping the firms attract and retain employees. Moreover, management can benchmark staff salaries against industry standards and requirements, which makes employees feel fairly compensated compared to other hotels. As stated by Mohrenweiser and Pfeifer (2023), employees consider perceived fairness pay by comparing their own wages, co-workers' wages, and wages of external firms, which consequently leads to job satisfaction.

Training & development were significant predictors that influenced retention in Sri Lanka. Therefore, management should prioritize training & development by investing in structured programs such as training in chemical handling, workplace safety, ergonomics, and customer service. Highlighted trainings are significant for housekeeping staff as they often involve risks in the workplace and interact with guests. As indicated by Alamsyah et al. (2024), training programs provided to housekeeping employees increase performance, satisfaction, and retention. They further emphasized a need for comprehensive training programs in cleaning techniques, customer service, and new technology. Likewise, Farrossabilla and Maksum (2025), Shiri et al. (2023), and Mishra (2023) acknowledged that the proper career programs maximize the employees' organizational commitment, motivation, and retention. Moreover, management should communicate clearly employee career progression, so employees see a future within the organization. This prevents alternatives like migration or seeking other available opportunities. Also, management should apply transparent career pathways for employees. Ahmed (2024) noted that career path transparency increases employee engagement while reducing turnover intention. Equally, hotels can use training as a recognition tool, such as linking employee skill development to promotions or pay

increases. Supporting this, Lassoued et al. (2022) claimed that the training programs should be linked with promotion, allowance, or bonus. Employee performance appraisals can be used as a fundamental tool to link training and development. Yet training requirements may differ between individuals. It is recommended to conduct at least 2 performance appraisals annually for staff. Kadiresan et al. (2015) emphasized that together with appraisals and training programs, they perform well, and when properly connected, they increase employee commitment and reduce turnover intentions.

Although supervisory support was not a significant predictor of retention in both countries, it is important in practice as it improves employee positivity, morale, and motivation. Supporting this, Milaad et al. (2025) outlined that supervisory support encourages employee engagement, emotional resilience, and motivation. Hence, the importance of supervisory support can be justified with qualitative insights provided by managers. Finnish management should encourage supervisors to act as mentors rather than provide guidelines or act as monitors. In contrast, in Sri Lanka, supervisors should be encouraged to provide constructive feedback. Also, supervisors should emphasize appreciation among staff in both contexts, which leads to a better work environment. Moreover, management can implement training for supervisors to uplift supervisory support, such as leadership training.

Although work-life balance was not a significant predictor of retention in Finland and Sri Lanka, in practice, it is an important benchmark in retention or turnover intention (Sumanarathna and Samarakoon, 2019; Gimpal, 2024; Heywood et al., 2010; Rajkumar et al., 2025; Cegarra-Leiva et al., 2012). It is commonly believed that flexible scheduling and appropriate day-offs can reduce turnover intention. Onken-Menke et al. (2018) found that flexible work practices increase organizational commitment and decrease turnover intention. Therefore, managers should implement flexible shifts aligned with both work requirements and staff obligations, particularly in Sri Lanka. Qualitative insights confirmed that hotel management in Sri Lanka was struggling to balance staff

family obligations and work requirements. A shift-swapping system can be implemented as a strategy where staff receive various shifts. In Finland, it is recommended to provide clear work schedules with predictable insights while allowing flexible time off. This matches the Finnish working culture and the country's regulations.

Since work stress did not significantly influence retention in Finland and Sri Lanka, the managers should focus on providing sources to manage it rather than trying to eliminate stress. Hence, the stress was normalized by the staff. Therefore, managers can provide better housekeeping tools and equipment, rest breaks during working, and support with manpower, which helps manage stress during busy times. As claimed by Quick and Henderson (2016), work stress cannot always be eliminated; it is normal and sometimes useful. Furthermore, authors suggest that rather than trying to eliminate stress, adopt strategies to manage, like implementing fair policies and a supportive work culture.

Although this study was conducted in Finland (developed) and Sri Lanka (emerging), the study findings still apply to other countries with similar contexts. For example, for Nordic countries and South asian countries like Sweden, Denmark, India, the Maldives, etc. Therefore, the highlighted managerial implications are useful for managers and HR practitioners in a similar context to Finland and Sri Lanka.

5.3. Limitations

A key limitation of this study is the low response rate among Finnish ground-level housekeeping staff compared to that in Sri Lanka. The deference reflects the reality of Finnish 3-star hotels. The hotels are smaller and therefore have fewer staff. Although the Finnish sample looks small, it actually covers half of the available population, confirming a 50% response rate. Babbie (1973) and Kidder (1981) justified that a 50% response rate in a survey is an acceptable and sufficient rate in social research. However, the lower Finnish response rate may weaken statistical analysis, particularly in regression. Therefore, findings should be seen as suggestive rather than definitive. To

address this limitation, the study adopted qualitative interviews to provide context for the quantitative results. This improves the overall validity of the study.

Another limitation of this study is the selection of 3-star hotels in Finland and Sri Lanka. All four hotels selected in Finland were in the Vaasa region, and all four in Sri Lanka were in the Central Province. This was because of the availability of access. Likewise, this does not fully represent all the 3-star hotels in Finland and Sri Lanka. Considering that, the results should be interpreted with caution, aligning with the broader Finnish and Sri Lankan hotel industry.

The data for the study were collected at one point in time (cross-sectional design). This can capture the perceptions, yet does not track changes in retention intention over time. Employee retention intention can change over time due to factors like promotions, policy changes, and personal commitments and circumstances. Domurath et al. (2023), a longitudinal study, found that employee turnover intention increases over time. Therefore, the selected approach was a limitation. Hence, this approach was chosen due to the time constraint. A longitudinal study would be a suitable approach as it can collect data at multiple points.

Although some qualitative interpretations were included with management insights, the study's main analysis was statistical regression. Thereby, the study may not be able to fully capture the employees' deep emotional or personal factors that influence retention. Employees' dignity, respect, and a hidden workplace culture can be noted as examples. Monteiro and Joseph (2023) highlighted that workplace culture is complex and, therefore, it is difficult to measure accurately using standardized tools.

5.4. Suggestions for Future Research

Future research could include other developed and emerging countries, or different regions, and or compare how these selected variables relate among other hotel

categories. Supporting this, Ghani et al. (2022) encourage future research comparisons of local versus international contexts. The current study was limited to Finland and Sri Lanka; instead, future research could be conducted using more developed and emerging countries. Likewise, future studies could focus on applying multiple regions in a country, whereas this study was limited to a region/province. The current study was based on 3-star hotels, which can be further expanded using other hotel segments, such as budget hotels and boutique hotels. This is consistent with Unsal-Akbıyık and Zeytinoglu (2018), who stated that future research could expand on investigating organizational culture and retention in boutique hotels. For instance, employees in a budget hotel may stay with their current job due to a stable salary, whereas boutique hotel employees stay considering the availability of career development.

This study was based on a selection of five organizational factors towards retention, including remuneration & rewards, training & development, work-life balance, supervisory support, and work stress. However, other prominent organizational factors may influence housekeeping employee retention, such as job satisfaction, job security, organizational culture, and workplace safety. Accordingly, future studies could explore how these organizational factors influence employee retention. Supporting this, Halim et al. (2021) noted that future studies should consider other variables, such as job motivation, organisational culture, burnout, and work autonomy, when investigating employee retention.

This study could also be extended by focusing on the managerial perspective or as a comparative study between housekeeping managers and ground-level staff. Although managers and staff represent the same department, their perceptions may vary. Staff may identify training & development as a significant predictor of retention, while managers may prefer better remuneration or a package. Aguilar-Escobar et al. (2021) argued that many hospitality studies still focus on task-level employee variables, which leaves a gap at the management level.

The current study was conducted among hotel housekeeping staff, who are often neglected in academic research. Likewise, some other departments were treated the same, such as the kitchen department, Spa, maintenance, and security. Therefore, future studies could be conducted based on these departments, which are still significant in the hospitality context.

Future studies could also be extended by selecting different types of employment. The current study was conducted based on full-time and part-time employees. However, hotels often outsource housekeeping staff from cleaning agencies. Therefore, future research could be conducted considering hotels' permanent staff and outsourced staff. All of them are important in housekeeping operations, who may have various perceptions about retention. Espino-Rodríguez (2023) goes beyond and recommends that future research could consider how outsourcing affects hotel permanent staff.

The current study model could be further expanded using Longitudinal studies. This is consistent with Meira et al. (2023), who stated that future studies should conduct longitudinal surveys. The current study employed a cross-sectional design, where data were collected at a single point in time. This was a limitation because employee retention intention could change over time due to different factors. A longitudinal method collects data at multiple points, allowing the capture of changes in retention intention over time.

The current study was based on employees' perception of retention derived from a survey questionnaire. Many existing studies measured employee retention or turnover based on survey questionnaires, where employees say whether they intend to stay or leave. Future research could consider actual company data, such as actual turnover rate, re-joining, duration of employee contracts, and compare with employee turnover intention. This is consistent with Ki and Choi-Kwon (2022), who studied employee turnover intention with actual data.

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Appendices

Appendix 01 – Privacy Note

Privacy Note

Study title

We kindly ask you to participate in this combined survey and interview study that investigates “A Comparative Study of Retention Factors Affecting Ground-Level Housekeeping Staff in Three-Star Hotels in Finland and Sri Lanka”.

After reading this privacy notice, you will be asked to consent to participate in the study. You may contact the researcher by email if you have questions.

Purpose of the study

The goal of the study is to identify workplace, social, economic, and managerial factors that influence staff decisions to stay with or leave their employer, and to develop recommendations to improve retention.

Research Schedule and Stages

The study will begin with an investigative survey in September 2025. This will be followed by complementary interviews with participants who have given their consent. The study consists of a survey and an interview part. The survey stage will map remuneration and rewards, work stress, training & development, work-life balance, and supervisory support's effect on retention. The interview stage will focus on the personal experiences of the interviewees.

The survey link will be emailed to housekeeping staff who have consented to participate in the study. Similarly, paper surveys will be distributed who are not able to provide email addresses. The survey will contain multiple-choice questions and take approximately 10 minutes to complete. The length of the interview will be 10 to 20 minutes. This can be arranged online or in person, and with the candidate's permission, the interview will be recorded.

Benefits and Risks Related to the Study

The results of this study can be used to improve ground-level housekeeping employee retention in hotel organizations, particularly in Finland and Sri Lanka. The methods used in the study do not carry financial risks, risks related to a company's reputation, or risks related to processing personal data.

Confidentiality, Processing, and Storing of Data

Data collected in this study will be processed confidentially according to the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union and the Finnish Data Protection Act. Similarly, the Sri Lankan Personal Data Protection Act, No. 9 of 2022 (PDPA) will be followed. Data will be stored and analyzed on secure computers and servers at the University of Vaasa or approved cloud services under data protection agreements.

Who will have access to your data:

- The Principal Investigator (Researcher)
- The University of Vaasa, Finland, including teaching and administrative staff involved in supervising, checking, and processing the thesis, and ensuring the research follows all rules and laws.
- Peer reviewers (only if this study turns into a journal article/ publication).
- Other academic collaborators, but only after all personal information that could identify you is removed (anonymized data).

Privacy of Persons/Privacy Protection in Publications

When reporting the results, subjects of interest and companies will be anonymised. Potentially identifiable parts will be omitted from examples.

The research file and the data collected in connection with the study will be stored at the University of Vaasa in accordance with the university's data management guidelines, after which they will be securely destroyed.

Voluntariness

As participating in the study is voluntary, you may withdraw at any stage. Declining to participate or withdrawing your participation will not cause prejudice regarding the services offered to you by the trade association/ hotel organization. If you cancel your participation, the data collected before the cancellation notice may still be used in the study.

Privacy in Research Publications and Publicity of the Study

The names of research subjects or companies will not be mentioned in connection with the study, as results will be fully anonymised. A summary of the results of the completed study will be sent to the research participants. The results will also be reported on the website, blog, and social media channels of the local trade association.

Non-Research and Further Research Use of Data

The collected data will be used for continuing education, such as for a doctoral thesis and publishing journal articles.

Further information:

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Appendix 02 – Informed Consent

Informed Consent

“I voluntarily consent to participate in this research project. I confirm that:

- I have read and understood the Privacy Notice for this study, or it has been read to me.
- I have had the chance to ask questions, and all my questions have been answered to my satisfaction.
- I understand what the study involves, including the types of data that will be collected (surveys, interviews, employment information).
- I understand that I can withdraw participation from this study at any stage without stating a reason. I may also withdraw my consent at any stage before the completion of the research project. If I withdraw my consent, the data I have provided until that point in time may still be used in the research project, but new data may no longer be used for research purposes. (NB: It is not possible to omit data related to a single research subject from research results after they have been analysed and published)

Participant name:

Participant signature:

Date:.....

Appendix 03 – Survey Questionnaire (English)

Survey questionnaire (English)

Instructions for Respondents

Please fill Section A -G. Tick where necessary. Indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement (Section B-G) by selecting a number from **1 to 5**, where: **1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree**

Section A: Background Information

- Gender: Male Female Other Prefer Not to say
- Employment type: Full-time Part-time
- Country: Finland Sri Lanka

Section B: Remuneration and Reward

	1	2	3	4	5
The rewards and recognition I receive from this job are attractive					
I am satisfied with the income I receive					
I am satisfied with the benefits I receive					

Section C: Training and Development

	1	2	3	4	5
When people start new jobs here, they are given enough guidance and training					
There is a commitment to ongoing training and development of staff					
The training and development I've received have improved my performance					

Section D: Work–Life Balance

	1	2	3	4	5
I can have a good balance between work and other activities					
I can be involved in both work and non-work-related activities					

My work allows me to have time for social activities outside of work					
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Section E: Supervisory Support

	1	2	3	4	5
My supervisor is helping me out with a work problem					
Supervisors are protective of and generous to loyal workers					
Decisions about changes in work methods are taken jointly by supervisors and employees					

Section F: Workplace Stress

	1	2	3	4	5
I find it difficult to do my job because of conflicting demands					
I feel uncertain about the exact scope of my duties and responsibilities at work					
Personality conflicts or strained relationships interfere with my ability to get quality work done					

Section G: Employee retention

	1	2	3	4	5
I am likely to still be working in this organisation in 2 years time					
I would like to still be working in this organisation in 5 years time					
I can see a future for me in this organisation					

Thank you!

Appendix 04 – Survey Questionnaire (Sinhala)

සමීක්ෂණ ප්‍රශ්නාවලිය (Survey questionnaire: Sinhala)

පිළිතුරු දෙන අය සඳහා උපදෙස්:

කරුණාකර A සිට G කොටස් පුරවන්න. අවශ්‍ය ස්ථානයේ “√” ලකුණ තබන්න. B සිට G කොටස් සඳහා, පහත පරිදි 1 සිට 5 දක්වා අංකයක් තෝරා, ඔබ එම ප්‍රකාශයට එකඟ වන අයුරින් හෝ එකඟ නොවන අයුරින් පෙන්වන්න:

1 = දැඩිව එකඟ නොවීම, 2 = එකඟ නොවීම, 3 = නොඑකඟ/එකඟ නොවන, 4 = එකඟ වීම, 5 = දැඩිව එකඟ වීම

කොටස A: ඔබේ තොරතුරු

ඔබ: පුරුෂ ස්ත්‍රී වෙනත් කිසිමට අකමැති

රැකියා වර්ගය: සම්පූර්ණ කාලීන අර්ධ කාලීන

රට: ශ්‍රී ලංකාව ඊළඟ රටක්

කොටස B: වැටුප් සහ ප්‍රසාද

මෙම රැකියාවෙන් ලබන ප්‍රසාද සහ පිළිගැනීම් ආකර්ෂණීය වේ	1	2	3	4	5
මම ලබන ආදායම පිළිබඳ සැහීමකට පත් වෙමි					
මම ලබන ප්‍රතිලාභ පිළිබඳ සැහීමකට පත් වෙමි					

කොටස C: පුහුණුව හා සංවර්ධනය

මෙහි නව රැකියා ආරම්භ කරන පුද්ගලයන්ට ප්‍රමාණවත් මාර්ගෝපදේශනය සහ පුහුණුව ලබා දේ	1	2	3	4	5
කාර්ය මණ්ඩලය සඳහා අධ්‍යයන පුහුණුව හා සංවර්ධන කටයුතු වලට කැපවීමක් පවතී					
මට ලැබුණු පුහුණුව සහ සංවර්ධන කටයුතු මගේ කාර්ය සාධනය වැඩි දියුණු කළේය					

කොටස D: රැකියා – ජීවිත සමතුලිතතාව

මට රැකියා සහ අනෙකුත් ක්‍රියාකාරකම් අතර සම්පූර්ණ සමතුලිතතාවක් ලබා ගත හැක	1	2	3	4	5
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මට රැකියා සහ රැකියා නොවන ක්‍රියාකාරකම් දෙකේම සහභාගී විය හැක					
මගේ රැකියාව මට රැකියා පිටත සමාජ ක්‍රියාකාරකම් සඳහා කාලය ලබා දේ					

කොටස E: අධීක්ෂණාත්මක (Supervisor) සහය

මගේ අධීක්ෂකයා රැකියා ගැටලුවකදී මට සහාය ලබා දේ	1	2	3	4	5
අධීක්ෂකයන් විශ්වාසවන්ත සේවකයන්ට ආරක්ෂාත්මක සහ උදාර ලෙස කටයුතු කරති					
රැකියා ක්‍රමවේදයන් වෙනස් කිරීම පිළිබඳ තීරණ අධීක්ෂකයින් සහ සේවකයින් එක්ව ගනිති					

කොටස F: රැකියා ආතතිය

පරස්පරවිරුද්ධ ඉල්ලීම් (conflicts) හේතුවෙන් මගේ රැකියාව කරන්න අපහසු වේ	1	2	3	4	5
මගේ කාර්යභාර සහ වගකීම් වල නියමිත ප්‍රමාණය පිළිබඳ අනතුරුදායකතාවක් ඇත					
පෞරුෂ ගැටුම් හෝ පීඩාකාරී සබඳතා නිසා ගුණාත්මක වැඩ කිරීමට මගේ හැකියාවට බාධා ඇති වේ.					

කොටස G: සේවක රඳවා ගැනීම

අනාගත වසර 2කදී මම තවමත් මෙම ආයතනයේ රැකියා කරනවා ඇතැයි මම සිතමි	1	2	3	4	5
අනාගත වසර 5කදී තවමත් මෙම ආයතනයේ රැකියා කිරීමට මම කැමතියි					
මම මෙම ආයතනය තුළ මගේ අනාගතය දැක ගනිමි					

ඔබට ස්තූතියි!

Appendix 05 – Survey Questionnaire (Finnish)

Kyselylomake (Suomi)

Ohjeet vastaajille:

Täytä osiot A–G. Merkitse rastilla tarvittaessa. Ilmoita, kuinka paljon olet samaa tai eri mieltä jokaisesta väittämästä (osiot B–G) valitsemalla numero väliltä 1–5, jossa:

1 = Täysin eri mieltä, 2 = Eri mieltä, 3 = Neutraali, 4 = Samaa mieltä, 5 = Täysin samaa mieltä

Osio A: Taustatiedot

Sukupuoli: Mies Nainen Muu En halua sanoa

Työsuhteen tyyppi: Kokoaikainen Osa-aikainen

Maa: Suomi Sri Lanka

Osio B: Palkka ja palkitseminen

	1	2	3	4	5
Työstä saamani palkkiot ja tunnustukset ovat houkuttelevia					
Olen tyytyväinen saamaani palkkaan					
Olen tyytyväinen saamiini etuuksiin					

Osio C: Koulutus ja kehittäminen

	1	2	3	4	5
Kun ihmiset aloittavat uuden työn täällä, he saavat riittävästi ohjausta ja koulutusta					
On sitoutumista henkilöstön jatkuvaan koulutukseen ja kehittämiseen					
Saamani koulutus ja kehitys ovat parantaneet suoritustani					

Osio D: Työ–elämä tasapaino

	1	2	3	4	5
Voin saavuttaa hyvän tasapainon työn ja muiden toimintojen välillä					
Voin osallistua sekä työ- että muuhun elämään liittyviin toimintoihin					

Työni antaa minulle aikaa sosiaaliseen toimintaan työn ulkopuolella					
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Osio E: Esimiehen tuki

	1	2	3	4	5
Esimieheni auttaa minua työongelman ratkaisemisessa					
Esimiehet suojelevat ja ovat anteliaita uskollisille työntekijöille					
Päätökset työmenetelmien muutoksista tehdään yhdessä esimiesten ja työntekijöiden kanssa					

Osio F: Työstressi

	1	2	3	4	5
Minun on vaikea tehdä työni ristiriitaisten vaatimusten vuoksi					
Tunnen epävarmuutta tarkasta tehtävänkuvastani ja vastuistani työssä					
Persoonallisuuserot tai kireät suhteet haittaavat mahdollisuuksiani tehdä laadukasta työtä					

Osio G: Työntekijöiden pysyvyys

	1	2	3	4	5
Todennäköisesti työskentelen tässä organisaatiossa vielä kahden vuoden kuluttua					
Haluaisin työskennellä tässä organisaatiossa vielä viiden vuoden kuluttua					
Näen tulevaisuuden itselleni tässä organisaatiossa					

Kiitos!

Appendix 06 – Structured Interview Questionnaire

Structured Interview Questionnaire

Section A: Respondent Background

- Name: _____
- Position & Hotel: _____

Section B: Remuneration and Rewards

1. How would you describe the current salary and benefits structure of housekeeping staff?
2. In your experience, how do remuneration and other rewards influence staff retention?
3. Are there additional reward strategies you believe could improve retention?
(**Probes:** Competitive pay, incentives, and fairness of rewards)

Section C: Work Stress

1. According to you, what are the main sources of stress for housekeeping staff?
2. How do these stressors affect staff retention?
3. What measures does the hotel take to reduce the work-related stress of housekeeping staff?
(**Probes:** Workload, shift patterns, physical demands, interpersonal conflicts)

Section D: Training and Development

1. How effective are the training and development programs provided to housekeeping staff?
2. According to you, do skill enhancements influence retention?
3. What additional training could improve staff motivation and retention?
(**Probes:** Induction, upskilling, cross-training, career growth)

Section E: Work-Life Balance

1. How do housekeeping staff in your hotel manage work-life balance?

2. Have you observed issues with scheduling, workload, or personal commitments affecting retention?
3. According to you, what policies/ practices have been effective in supporting staff work-life balance?

(**Probes:** Shift flexibility, leave policies, personal time accommodations)

Section F: Supervisory Support

1. How would you describe the role of supervisors in supporting housekeeping staff retention?
2. In your experience, how do supervisory behaviours affect staff satisfaction?
3. Can you provide examples of effective supervisory support that lead to staff retention?

(**Probes:** Feedback, mentorship, conflict resolution, recognition)

Section G: Retention

1. In your opinion, what are the main factors that contribute to housekeeping staff retention?
2. Is there anything else you would like to share about factors influencing retention?
3. What strategic changes would you recommend to improve retention?

(**Probes:** key factors, other factors, strategies)

Thank you!

Appendix 07 – Qualitative Data Analysis

Theme	Sub-theme	Code	Direct quote (FIN & SL) & Interviewee
Remuniration & Rewards	Financial Motivation	Salary satisfaction & fair pay	<p>FIN: “It is fair and satisfactory, as I hear from my employees.” & “We do not have any staff turnover issues; they even ask for more working hours; we do not have any employees resigning because of salary reasons.” (Interviewee 1)</p> <p>“I am happy.” (Interviewee 3)</p> <p>SL: “As a mid-chain hotel [...], in par with other hotels, we are happy, it is not only the remuneration part, [...] about the overall package” (Interviewee 2)</p> <p>“Compared to the past, at present staff (ex, interns) have been paid a fair salary, also a package including free accommodation and food” & “If they are satisfied with salary & package, they are more likely to be retained” (Interviewee 4)</p> <p>“I am not 100% happy with the salary. Before 1 half a year ago, staff had a good income, but with the new VAT%, staff are getting a lower service charge [...] service charge dropped by half” & “If staff’s income does not match their expenses, they are more</p>

			<p>likely to leave” (Interviewee 6)</p> <p>“Compared to other industries, I believe staff get a good salary, including free uniform, accommodation, tips, and they affect employee retention.” (Interviewee 5)</p>
	Reward Strategies	Incentives & Bonuses	<p>FIN: “It is fair and satisfactory, as I hear from my employees.” (Interviewee 1)</p> <p>“I am happy.” (Interviewee 3)</p> <p>SL: “We are guaranteed [...] service charge, basic salary, something called minimum guaranteed salary.”, “It's affected (remuneration), but what I believe at the end is, more than remuneration, we should provide them a safe environment.”, “We reward whenever possible [...], recently we had International Housekeeping-week, we celebrated [...], our staff won a second place at one of the events, and after that we gave them another reward’ (Interviewee 2)</p> <p>“We have discussed the increase of incentives and salaries with GM/Management, they often increase according to staff performance appraisals yearly.” & “If we can offer something like bonuses, staff</p>

			are more likely to stay with their current job” (Interviewee 6)
Training & Development	Skill Enhancement	Induction, upskilling, cross-training	<p>FIN: “When they start, they go through quite extensive training programs.” & “Also, we provide safety training very regularly” & “once every half year, we get a visit from a qualified trainer” (Interviewee 1)</p> <p>“I do provide training”, “no additional training needed, they work perfectly, now for a long time [...], now everybody knows what to do” (Interviewee 3)</p> <p>SL: “Whatever training is possible, we do give [...] when we feel candidates need further training [...], we put them on training, by that we are able to retain staff”, “We are closely working with big hotels, namely, Grand hotel, Hill club, Araliya group, we are connected with their forums [...] whenever we have workshops with them, we refer our staff there”, “When they're fully trained [...], there is a high degree of chances they can get into a five-star hotel [...] or they can easily migrate”(Interviewee 2)</p> <p>“Especially, if someone comes as a trainee or without experience, they are normally not open, they</p>

			<p>don't ask questions and clarifications, so first we allow them to get familiar with the working environment and then step by step we provide training” (Interviewee 5)</p> <p>“We received lots of training [...], for example, chemical and room making” (Interviewee 6)</p>
	Career Growth	Extensive path & Personal development	<p>FIN: “We are providing quite an extensive path for their career development,” & “They are receiving all the training they need” (Interviewee 1)</p> <p>SL: “We provide training for personal development. For example, when trainees come with basic knowledge, we help them to develop, and staff who work with us have already developed their skills and knowledge.” (Interviewee 4)</p>
Work Stress	Workload & Physical Demands	Heavy workload & quality, early check-ins, long shifts	<p>FIN: “Time is quite tight, especially during the summer season, and second, the quality standards that we have to follow.” (Interviewee 1)</p> <p>“Some days we are really stressed because there is a lot of cleaning and a lot comes in.” & “Sometimes we have fewer cleaners.” (Interviewee 3)</p>

			<p>SL: “Early check-ins lead to workload and stress as it has limited time to clean a room.” (Interviewee 5)</p> <p>“I don’t think they have a kind of stress [...] we have given enough manpower what is required” & “they are not complaining, saying I have too much work” (Interviewee 2)</p> <p>“Staff get stressed when peak-season comes, because of more work [...], for example, mini bar activities” (Interviewee 5)</p> <p>“Houskeeping is hard work [...] we have problems with late check-outs and with back-to-back arrivals [...] we don't have enough time to prepare rooms, also we can not ask guests to leave who stay, and similarly can't satisfy those who are coming, accordingly work stress arises, but in this case, we do teamwork [...] such placing more people where busy” (Interviewee 6)</p>
	Interpersonal Stress	Conflicts & pressure	<p>FIN: “Sometimes I talk to my boss, say: we really need more (staff)” & [...] she takes more” (Interviewee 3)</p> <p>SL: “We have to understand them (staff), their expectation and requirements, say, if a</p>

			<p>person wants to take a leave for personal work, definitely we have to cater to that one, otherwise, he is going to work under pressure” (Interviewee 2)</p>
Work-Life Balance	Scheduling & Flexibility	Shift flexibility & day-offs	<p>FIN: “Every shift has a maximum hour it can last; our employees get resting time according to the collective agreements.” (Interviewee 1)</p> <p>“We have only daytime work here; sometimes we get, but usually Monday to Friday.” “The manager is here, flexible.” (Interviewee 3)</p> <p>SL: “We are giving them needed day-offs monthly [...] when we compare to bigger hotels and small hotels all [...], even bigger hotels give six days off, we are giving them eight days per month, also we have designed their shifts dynamically [...] for them to come up with their plans” (Interviewee 2)</p> <p>“We provide day-offs on time, and provide request-offs, which leads to balancing family life” (Interviewee 4)</p>
	Personal Commitments	Family & Study obligations	<p>FIN: “For example, if a person enrolls in the studies [...]; resign” (Interviewee 1)</p> <p>SL: “I tell my staff to bring your family for a meal stay at my other properties [...], when</p>

			<p>we create a connection with that type of relationship with a family, it's easy for our team to concentrate on work" (Interviewee 2)</p> <p>"Personal commitments, like distance to home, available time to be involved with family, affect staff retention" (Interviewee 4)</p> <p>"Due to family issues & personal problems, some staff were leaving jobs" (Interviewee 5)</p>
Supervisory Support	Recognition & Mentorship	Feedback & Guidance	<p>FIN: "A good supervisor is a person who keeps promises and a person the employee can rely on" & "Staff are satisfied when they are assessed in a justice way, and they are not being provided negative feedback, but also positive feedback" (Interviewee 1)</p> <p>"I always try to say, [...] good job, example, make the bed nicely" [...] I tried to be nice." (Interviewee 3)</p> <p>SL: "Rather than just providing feedback or guidance, if a supervisor can show and demonstrate actions by themselves, I believe it is a good way of practice, so that staff can capture and learn more" & "My mentoring helped some staff to reach better opportunities, for example, now some are</p>

			<p>working in Hilton, Radisson, Dubai, and the UK” (Interviewee 4)</p> <p>“As I see, a supervisor is the person who inspires staff, and such should be leading by example [...]. If so, it is easy to guide the team” (Interviewee 5)</p>
	Leadership Behavior	Approachability & Problem-solving	<p>FIN: “Supervisor is a leader and a good leader; for example, he not only provides theory and practice, but also actively participates in employees' everyday tasks”, “Supports solving many difficulties”, “we got a situation, because of personal reasons, a person couldn't do a certain shift, so not to reduce he/her hours, I offered shifts in other places” & “we are trying to observe each other and take care of our well-being” (Interviewee 1)</p> <p>“We do not have gossip like something [...], I will say something bothers me [...] I don't talk about behind” (Interviewee 3)</p> <p>SL: “If a supervisor wants to say something to his staff, but if he feels sometimes that if I say, this one may be misunderstood, I can't get the work done, then we (management) just address that problem” (Interviewee 2)</p>

			<p>“I believe the way a supervisor behaves directly affects staff satisfaction, for example, how you talk and engage” (Interviewee 4)</p> <p>“According to my knowledge, staff stay if the supervisor behaves well, such as their relationship is important [...], for example, if I leave one hotel for another, there are several staff who are willing to come with me” (Interviewee 5)</p>
Retention	Staff Commitment	Loyalty & intention to stay	<p>FIN: “Actually, we don’t have any staff turnover.” (Interviewee 1)</p> <p>“For example, if a person enrolls in the studies, this is the only reason faced (Resigned); not that someone changed the work because they found something better.” (Interviewee 1)</p> <p>“We are like family here” (Interviewee 3)</p> <p>SL: “If the staff is not happy, they are going to go, even if it is the same for us” (Interviewee 2)</p> <p>“I believe young people are more likely to stay if they receive new knowledge. But, when it comes to middle age, they are more dependent on salary” (Interviewee 5)</p>

			<p>“A good salary, accommodation, and work environment maximize staff retention and reduce staff leaving the job” (Interviewee 4)</p>
	Organizational Factors	Culture & Environment	<p>FIN: “General work satisfaction, good work-life balance, satisfactory salary, and the possibility of development.” & “This is a very good company when it comes to working atmosphere” (Interviewee 1)</p> <p>“We go hang out twice a year” (Interviewee 3)</p> <p>SL: “Example, if I have been treated unfairly [...], that kind of situation [...], even other factors met [...], there is a high degree of questionable retention” (Interviewee 2)</p> <p>“At present, remuneration is a highly considerable factor when a person chooses an employment, considering living costs, especially in Sri Lanka” (Interviewee 4)</p> <p>“I think staff are more interested in developing, so we need to show them how to reach their targets within a timeframe [...]. If we do so, I believe they will stay” (Interviewee 5)</p>